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Can fiscal rules improve banking system stability in developing countries?

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Abstract

This paper investigates the causal impact of fiscal rules on banking system stability in developing countries. Using a panel of 62 developing economies over the period 1990–2020, the authors assess whether adopting a fiscal rule contributes to reducing the level of non-performing loans, a key indicator of banking vulnerability. The analysis relies on entropy balancing to ensure covariates balance between treated and control groups. Results indicate that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces the ratio of non-performing loans, with an average treatment effect of approximately 0.97 percentage points. The study identifies multiple transmission channels—sovereign credit ratings, income inequality reduction, and macroeconomic stabilization—through which fiscal rules indirectly strengthen banking stability. Heterogeneity analysis reveals that the effect varies by the type and duration of the rule and by structural financial characteristics. This research contributes to the literature by extending the role of fiscal rules beyond debt and deficit control, framing them as institutional anchors for financial stability in fiscally and economically vulnerable contexts.

Keywords: • Fiscal rules • Banking stability • Developing countries
• Entropy balancing.

JEL Codes: F34, G1, H63.

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1 Introduction

Coronavirus crisis has increased the risk of debt distress in developing countries. Debt levels reached record levels during the pandemic and the war between Russia and Ukraine may exacerbate the problem. Today, 60% of countries eligible for the Debt Service Suspension Initiative (DSSI) are considered to be at high risk of debt distress or are already in debt distress. Fragile and conflict-affected states (FAS) and small island developing states (SIDS) were particularly hard hit by the 2020 recession and their fiscal space was significantly eroded. While developing countries' governments adopted fiscal responses to counter the economic and social impact of the pandemic, some faced the constraints imposed by fiscal rules adopted in the past to ensure fiscal discipline. Other countries have benefited from the fiscal space created by positive savings that they had accumulated in good times through fiscal rules. This new dynamic has brought back to the center of attention issues related to the management of fiscal policy and the implications of fiscal rules for the rest of the macroeconomic environment of countries. In the literature, an important body of theoretical and empirical research develops the link between monetary policy and financial stability through bank balance sheets ([Bernanke and Gertler, 1995](#); [Albertazzi et al., 2020](#); [Barnea et al., 2015](#); [Smets, 2018](#); [Lamers et al., 2019](#)). At the same time, there is a remarkable lack of work on the channels through which fiscal rules can affect bank balance sheets and financial stability despite the fact that experience demonstrates that there is potentially a clear link between the two. In fact, financial crises have been preceded by high levels of public debt linked to inefficient public financial management due to the lack of discipline imposed by fiscal rules. The increase in fiscal risk due to the lack of fiscal rules, on the other hand, can potentially weaken the financial system by weakening the balance sheets of banks holding government debt and by limiting the ability of authorities to pursue countercyclical policies. The increase in sovereign risk associated with weak fiscal discipline also reduces the value of government securities eligible as collateral and the value of explicit and implicit government guarantees. Indeed, a downgrade of a sovereign credit rating normally translates into a downgrade of banks, since the sovereign issuer rating normally constitutes a "ceiling" for corporate ratings. Add to this, a credit downgrade can weaken banks indirectly, through its impact on the economy in general. It may increase the cost of market financing, as the yield on sovereign debt generally provides a floor for the cost of private financing. The close link between banks and public sector balance sheets, in both directions, can also lead to a spiral of negative interactions. Thus, sovereign risk through lack of fiscal discipline and financial

risk are mutually reinforcing, as evidenced by the recent debt crisis in the euro area.

More generally, governments and their fiscal rules can interact directly with the banking system as market players when financing their budget deficits and managing their debt. For example, parameters such as the amount and maturity of public debt held by banks, sovereign credit ratings, the proportion of public debt insured via credit default swap markets, and the share of interbank lending covered by government securities as collateral can be taken into account when assessing the relationship between fiscal policies and banking stability. In addition, the government plays a key role as fiscal authority, affecting the behavior of banking sector players through tax structures. More specifically, appropriate fiscal rules can contribute to banking stability in several ways. Fiscal rules can contribute to a high level of confidence in banks and financial markets through the responsible and sustainable conduct of fiscal policy. They can create fiscal room for maneuver to ensure a strong capacity for debt repayment and crisis intervention. They can also provide sound incentives for the owners and managers of banking institutions, as well as for the economy as a whole, in conjunction with tax and spending structures, and create restrictive rules for granting financial assistance to financial institutions to limit moral hazard behavior. Also, as the indirect links between fiscal policies and the financial sector, via non-financial corporations or households, are extensive, fiscal rules may have even greater consequences for banking stability than direct links. The fiscal rules that govern budgetary policies can represent a risk to financial stability if they threaten the functioning of the real economy. On the other hand, they contribute to banking stability as long as they support healthy overall economic development. There is also the fact that the perceived stability of a country's banking system may depend on the financial strength of the government supporting it, which in turn is influenced by the extent of recognized and conditional government support already given to the financial system. Consequently, fiscal and banking risks in a country may not be totally dissociable.

Based on these observations, our study analyzes the interaction between fiscal rules, which are a key component of fiscal policy, and financial stability. It focuses mainly on the impact of fiscal rules on the dynamics of NPLs of banks. The choice to focus only on the banking sector is justified by the fact that domestic banks in developing countries increasingly hold government securities on their balance sheets. Thus, fiscal discipline in public finances induced by the adoption of fiscal rules will necessarily have implications on the balance sheets of banks in the countries that adopt them. This choice is also justified by the fact that financial markets are not well developed in developing countries, making banks the heart of the financial system. The NPL is a common indicator to measure credit

risk because it directly affects the banking system. The Asian financial crisis of 1997 and the global crisis of 2007 are the two examples that best explain how NPLs can affect the financial system (Balima and Sy, 2021; Reinhart and Rogoff, 2011; Qian et al., 2011, Messai and Jouini, 2013; Makri et al., 2014) pointed out that NPLs can be an indicator of the onset of a banking and financial crisis, as they negatively impact the financial system. A low level of NPLs indicates a strong financial system, while a high level of NPLs may indicate a vulnerable financial system.

To identify the causal impact of fiscal rules on NPLs, we use entropy balancing, an impact analysis method recently developed by Hainmueller (2012). Based on a large sample of 62 developing countries over the period 1990-2020, we show that fiscal rules are an effective instrument for reducing NPLs and a good stabilizer of the financial system in developing countries. This result is robust to a battery of tests.

This study offers a significant contribution by reinterpreting fiscal rules as instruments of financial stabilization in the context of structurally fragile banking systems in developing countries. Unlike conventional frameworks that view fiscal rules primarily as tools for budgetary discipline, this work proposes a conceptual model where fiscal rules also serve as institutional levers for mitigating systemic banking vulnerabilities. In developing economies, banks often operate in environments marked by high exposure to sovereign risk, dependence on public sector financing, and limited credit portfolio diversification. In such settings, fiscal uncertainty—manifested through persistent deficits, unpredictable public spending, and inflationary pressures—exacerbates financial fragility by undermining bank profitability and solvency. By institutionalizing budgetary discipline, fiscal rules contribute to reducing macroeconomic volatility, improving sovereign credit ratings, and enhancing policy predictability. These mechanisms collectively lower the probability of sovereign default and reduce balance sheet contagion to the banking sector. Moreover, in financial systems where public or semi-public institutions dominate credit allocation, fiscal rules can also help curtail politically motivated lending and the accumulation of public sector arrears. In this way, fiscal rules function as macroeconomic credibility anchors, shaping expectations, limiting opportunistic behavior, and fostering more efficient credit allocation within the banking sector. This paper expands the traditional scope of fiscal policy by situating it at the intersection of macroeconomic governance and financial system resilience, offering new insights into how fiscal frameworks can enhance banking stability in vulnerable developing economies.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. The following section discusses previous studies. Section 3 discusses the conception issues of fiscal rules and bank NPLs.

The data is described in Section 4. The empirical methodology is discussed in Section 5. The main findings are presented in Section 6. Sections 7 and 8 analyze the sensitivity and heterogeneity of our results, respectively. Section 9 presents some empirical evidence on the main channels. Finally, Section 10 concludes the study.

2 Literature review

Since the early 90s, macroeconomic policies based on fiscal rules have become increasingly important throughout the world in general, and in developing countries in particular. A growing number of countries have adopted fiscal rules to guide the management of their fiscal policies, with the idea of achieving balanced budgets over the medium and long term, which are difficult to guarantee because of discretionary policies. The main objective of implementing fiscal rules is the same: to bring credibility to the management of fiscal (and, more generally, macroeconomic) policies by eliminating discretionary intervention. The impact of these fiscal rules has been widely examined in the literature in several different regional contexts: for OECD countries (Dahan and Strawczynski, 2010), for Europe (Debrun, 2000; Debrun et al., 2008; Bayoumi et al., 1994; Poterba and Rueben, 1997), for Swiss cantons and municipalities (Feld and Kirchgässner, 2008; Krogstrup and Wälti, 2008) and for developing countries (Combes et al., 2017; Sawadogo, 2020; Apeti et al., 2024; Apeti et al., 2025; Combes et al., 2024; Tapsoba, 2012, etc). Overall, this literature shows that the adoption of fiscal rules enables a country's macroeconomic fundamentals to remain solid and stable. Indeed, governments may have incentives to overspend in certain circumstances. For example, governments may view active public spending as a means of countering significant private spending gaps in times of economic depression, or as a means of reducing the intensity of business cycles (Pieschacón, 2012; Mihalyi and Fernández, 2018). In addition, given that the rapid increase of countries' public debt is often attributable to excessive spending (Imbeau and Pétry, 2004), fiscal rules can be an important anchor for long-term fiscal sustainability. Consequently, fiscal rules generally aim to correct distorted incentives and contain pressures to exceed current government revenues to ensure fiscal responsibility and debt sustainability. Fiscal rules can therefore act to prevent excessive debt by limiting incentives to overspend (Alfaro and Kanczuk, 2017; Aguiar and Amador, 2016). The rules thus limit excessive deficits, strengthen the credibility of fiscal policy, minimize negative effects on external relations and ensure the sustainability of public finances in order to provide more disciplined macroeconomic conditions (Combes et al., 2014; Wyplosz, 2012; Debrun et al., 2008; Afonso and Hauptmeier,

2009) find that fiscal rules increase the cyclically-adjusted primary balance and support the credit line. In other words, fiscal rules improve the discretionary position of fiscal policy due to numerical constraints and increased structural surplus. Using US data, (Poterba, 1995) finds that fiscal rules play an important role in creating short-term deficit dynamics. The stricter the rules, the larger the government surplus and the smaller the deficit. In the same logic (Bayoumi and Eichengreen, 1995; Alesina and Bayoumi, 1996) shows that fiscal rules in the USA are a source of credibility, and thus lead to improved macroeconomic stability. However, it is also important to mention that fiscal rules are also subject to criticism. They can encourage pro-cyclical fiscal policy or creative accounting that reduces overall budget transparency (Debrun et al., 2008) While the financial crisis of 2008 has led to more research into the relationship between the banking sector and government in dynamic stochastic general equilibrium (DSGE) models, the literature on the interactions between the banking sector and fiscal rule is very limited. The existing literature is more general and concerns potential relationships between the financial sector and the government (Angeloni and Wolff, 2012) propose a DSGE model in which they integrate a banking sector and a government sector with the aim of analyzing the consequences of a fiscal adjustment on banking stability. Their results show that, compared with expenditure-based consolidations, tax-based policies exhibit faster debt adjustment, but at the expense of higher swings in leverage and bank risk (Dib, 2010a; Dib, 2010b; Darracq Pariès et al., 2010) also present DSGE models that include both a banking and a government sector. The results show that fiscal policy affects the banking sector in particular by creating impulsive reactions of bank balance sheet items in response to structural shocks to government spending (Krishnamurthy and Vissing-Jorgensen, 2012) show that an indirect channel through which fiscal policy affects banks is linked to the macroeconomic effects of fiscal consolidation. If fiscal adjustment leads to an economic slowdown, this would increase the probability of NPLs. If these effects are significant, we should see more investment in government securities when a country enters a period of fiscal consolidation. They also show that bank liquidity is an important determinant of demand for government bonds. The Bank for International Settlements has published a report analyzing the impact of sovereign risk on the banking system. It highlights the main transmission channels on banks' financing conditions. In particular, the BIS shows that the increase in sovereign risk is detrimental to banks¹. As banks' balance sheet funding is weakened, financing becomes more expensive. Banks can therefore react to changes in sovereign risk by making asset-side adjustments, i.e. changes in portfolio composition.

¹<https://www.bis.org/publ/arpdf/ar2016e5.pdf>

Similarly, a fiscal adjustment should stimulate banks' interest in government securities, as treasuries are perceived as safer after a fiscal consolidation. At the same time, banks' perception of sovereign risk is likely to depend on various determinants, including the current state of public finances and the economy, as well as the outlook for future developments.

3 Fiscal rules and bank NPLs: Conceptual issues

3.1 *Definition and typology of fiscal rules*

Basically, fiscal rules were established by citizens, as taxpayers, with regard to governments in order to control the possible misuse of tax money and the waste of resources (Von Hagen, 2002). Most of these rules were drawn up in the 1990s by a team led by Lledó et al. (2017) in response to the deteriorating budgetary situation in many advanced economies after a very long period of increased public spending which began in the 1970s². Fiscal rules can be defined as legislative agreements designed to control fiscal policy with the aim of ensuring macroeconomic sustainability and stability (Lledó et al., 2017; Grembi et al., 2016). Subsequently, fiscal rules emerged and spread worldwide in the wake of the global financial crisis: they are more applicable, more flexible and more operational than their predecessors (Schelker and Eichenberger, 2010).

According to Lledó et al. (2017), at the macroeconomic level, a fiscal rule can be formally defined as a permanent constraint on fiscal policy, expressed in terms of fixed numerical limits (floors or ceilings) on an overall fiscal performance indicator set in legislation and binding for at least three years. These rules have only one main objective, to mitigate budget deficit bias and promote fiscal discipline by reducing the scope for policymakers to constrain decisions on spending and revenue programs. The rules therefore help to correct incentives to overspend, particularly during periods of business cycle growth, while seeking to ensure fiscal responsibility, long-term debt sustainability and intergenerational equity.

Indeed, most rules are generally implemented at national or sub-national level, although supranational rules have also been introduced over the last two decades to avoid tax behavior incompatible with the common needs of countries that are part of a monetary union³. In this paper we work only on national fiscal rules, the reasons for which

²Historically, until 1990, only five countries had fiscal rules: Germany, Indonesia, Japan, Luxembourg and the United States.

³This is the case of the European Union, the Eastern Caribbean Currency Union, the West African Economic and Monetary Union and the Central African Economic and Monetary Community.

are explained in Section 4 below. We distinguish four types of fiscal rule implemented in countries as fiscal reform (see [Lledó et al., 2017](#); [Kopits and Symansky, 1998](#)).

- **Budget balance rules (BBR)** or deficit rules. These types of rules impose a balance between public revenues and non-financial public expenditure in order not to generate a deficit (or a limit is set for the public deficit as a percentage of GDP), in structural terms (a balance is required between cyclically-adjusted revenues and non-financial expenditure, or a limit is set for the structural deficit as a percentage of GDP), or by establishing rules concerning the balance between revenues and current expenditure, according to which debt-related expenditure is not calculated and is exempt from the budget constraint.

- **Debt rules (DR)**. They accompany the debt policy by setting a limit on the volume of gross or net debt as a function of GDP and/or defining a target for the reserves of an extra-budgetary reserve fund.

- **Expenditure rules (ER)**. They accompany the debt policy by setting a limit on the volume of gross or net debt as a function of GDP and/or defining a target for the reserves of an extra-budgetary reserve fund.

- **Revenue rules (RR)**. They establish ceilings or floors for public revenues, with the aim of increasing revenue collection and/or avoiding an excessive tax burden.

In most cases, these rules are used in combination to mitigate their respective disadvantages and combine their advantages. The advantages and disadvantages of each type of rule have been established by [Schaechter et al. \(2012\)](#), who demonstrated that none can achieve all objectives individually. For example, revenue rules are generally difficult to implement due to their complex nature for developing countries. In any case, the usefulness of different types of fiscal rules may depend on their final formulation and/or degree of compliance, which requires analysis.

3.2 *Bank non-performing loans*

Bank non-Performing Loans (Bank NPLs) refer to loans whose repayments are 90 days or more overdue, or which are deemed uncollectible. According to the [IMF \(2013\)](#)⁴, bank NPLs are a key indicator of the vulnerability of the banking sector and, more broadly, of the real economy. Since the bursting of the real estate and stock market bubble in Japan in 1990, when bank NPLs paralyzed the banking sector for over a decade, followed by the 2008 financial crisis "subprime" marked by the rise of bank NPLs, a credit crunch in

⁴<https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/Staff-Discussion-Notes/Issues/2016/12/31/A-Strategy-for-Resolving-Europes-Problem-Loans-41018>

the United States which subsequently spread and became a global recession, numerous studies have attempted to analyze the macroeconomic factors behind bank NPLs. For example, [Nkusu \(2011\)](#) found a strong negative correlation between GDP growth and bank NPLs levels. They find that during recessions, the repayment capacity of companies and households falls, increasing defaults. The interest rate situation was analyzed by [Beck et al. \(2010\)](#) shortly after the “subprime” crisis. The authors find that high rates increase debt servicing, exacerbating defaults. Moreover, they find that the effect is more pronounced in countries where variable-rate credit was dominant. Furthermore, [Louzis et al. \(2012\)](#) show that country-specific factors, such as the quality of legal institutions or banking governance, play a decisive role. In a study of 26 emerging countries, [Nkusu \(2011\)](#) shows that deteriorating economic conditions (notably falling GDP and rising unemployment) are closely linked to rising bank NPLs. The author highlights the delayed effect of these macroeconomic shocks on bank credit quality, underlining the amplifying role of financial channels. Analyzing Greek banking data, [Louzis et al. \(2012\)](#) identify three key macroeconomic variables: GDP, unemployment and interest rates. Their study reveals that household and corporate bank NPLs react differently to economic shocks, highlighting the importance of segmenting credit portfolios in analyses. [Klein \(2013\)](#) focuses on Eastern European countries and concludes that the rise in the bank NPLs ratio is mainly due to weak economic growth post-2008 crisis. The author stresses the interaction between macroeconomic factors and institutional quality: an inefficient judicial system and a rigid bankruptcy framework hinder the resolution of bad loans. In the same vein, [Laeven and Levine \(2009\)](#) show that weak banking regulations encourage the accumulation of risky loans. [Bonin et al. \(2005\)](#), reach a similar conclusion that state-owned or politically-controlled banks are more exposed to the accumulation of bank NPLs. In the spirit of [Espinoza and Prasad \(2010\)](#), banks operating in economies with high oil volatility are particularly sensitive to external shocks. They highlight a strong link between non-oil growth, oil price variations and deterioration in the quality of banking assets. Poor banking governance also accentuates the phenomenon.

3.3 The fiscal rules transmission mechanisms into bank NPLs

The channels through which fiscal rules affect NPLs is ambiguous in the literature. This may be because empirical analyses assessing the impact of macroeconomic institutions on policy outcomes have tended to consider fiscal and monetary policies in isolation. It is this unfounded dichotomy that we intend to explore through the analysis of transmission channels in this sub-section. The main channels through which fiscal rules could affect

banks' NPLs are shown in graph 1. Fiscal rules could affect NPLs due to their impact on the budget deficit and effect of corporate leverage. Indeed, higher leverage makes default more likely, which tends to increase NPLs (Ghosh, 2015a). Fiscal rules, by imposing effective restrictions to prevent governments from running excessive deficits and accumulating unsustainable levels of debt, reduce the leverage that would be noticeable on banks' asset quality. In addition, effective adoption of fiscal rules can strengthen the power and decision-making of the monetary authorities and prevent leverage from increasing as domestic credit growth rises. Intuitively, an increase in leverage contributes to a higher risk premium on the lending rate and the rate of return on equity, which constitute the real cost of capital. The literature shows that the unemployment rate has a positive impact on NPLs (see, Dimitrios et al., 2016). In fact, rising unemployment is making more borrowers unable to meet their debts. Fiscal rules, by reducing fiscal policy discretion (Fatás and Mihov, 2006), improve access to financial markets (Sawadogo, 2020), increase public and private investment which in turn boosts economic growth by reducing macroeconomic volatility (Fatás and Mihov, 2006), and eradicate unemployment. As a result, they will reduce NPLs due to increased economic activity.

Fiscal policy, characterized by tightly controlled deficits and sustainable debt, fosters a stable economic environment favorable to economic growth (De Grauwe, 2025). Consequently, robust economic growth translates into increased demand for credit, as businesses and households become more confident regarding the future and their income prospects. Banks benefit directly from this growth dynamic. In times of economic expansion, firms are more inclined to borrow to finance their investments, and consumers are more likely to apply for consumer credit, as their financial situation is stronger. Banks, which play a key role in financial intermediation, then see their margins strengthen, as demand for credit increases and the credit quality of borrowers improves. On the other hand, if fiscal rules are not respected and public spending is excessive, this can lead to high fiscal deficits and rising public debt. Such conditions can lead to economic fragility, characterized by higher interest rates, higher inflation or unstable financial markets. An uncertain or declining economic environment can limit demand for credit, as companies and households become more reluctant to borrow due to uncertain economic prospects. Banks may then find themselves faced with a decline in lending activity and an increase in borrower risk, due to a deterioration in their creditworthiness.

Income inequality plays a crucial role in shaping financial vulnerabilities, particularly through its impact on the quality of bank loan portfolios. Several mechanisms help explain this relationship. First, in highly unequal economies, low-income households are more

exposed to economic shocks and have limited financial buffers, increasing their likelihood of defaulting on loans (Agnello et al., 2012; IMF, 2017). Second, stagnant earnings among lower-income groups can drive increased reliance on credit to sustain consumption levels, often leading to unsustainable debt burdens (Rajan, 2010). Third, public policies or banking strategies aiming to “compensate” for inequality by expanding access to credit may result in lower lending standards, thereby increasing the accumulation of risky loans (Rajan, 2010; Demirgüç-Kunt and Levine, 2009). Lastly, inequality undermines aggregate demand and slows economic growth, which in turn raises the default risk among firms and contributes to the growth of non-performing loans on bank balance sheets (Ostry et al., 2014; Dabla-Norris et al., 2015). In this way, income inequality affects both micro-level repayment capacity and broader macroeconomic dynamics, making it a structural determinant of financial stability.

Fiscal rules adoption is a central lever of macroeconomic discipline that can have indirect effects on financial stability by reducing income inequalities. By imposing stricter management of public finances, fiscal rules limit excessive deficits and encourage a more efficient allocation of resources (Apeti et al., 2025), notably to social spending. This makes them a major shift in public financial management, with implications that go far beyond mere budgetary sustainability. By requiring governments to adhere to limits on deficits, debt, or public spending, fiscal rules promote fiscal discipline and can significantly reshape the composition of public expenditures. Several studies—including Bastagli et al. (2012) and Woo et al. (2013)—show that when well-designed and effectively implemented, fiscal rules can reinforce redistributive policies by reallocating resources toward socially productive sectors such as education, health care, and targeted transfers. Accordingly, the adoption of such rules contributes to a reduction in income inequality (Dabla-Norris et al., 2015; Combes et al., 2024). Lower inequality enhances the financial resilience of low-income households, reduces their dependence on credit to maintain consumption, and lowers their probability of loan default. Downstream, this translates into a reduced stock of bank NPLs in the banking system (IMF, 2017). Agnello et al. (2012) further emphasize that credible and well-enforced fiscal rules help reduce macroeconomic volatility, which in turn lowers systemic risk and strengthens the quality of bank loan portfolios. In sum, the adoption of fiscal rules—when accompanied by credible institutional frameworks and an inclusive policy orientation—not only enhances public finance sustainability, but also promotes financial stability through an often-overlooked transmission channel: income inequality.

Regarding sovereign credit rating, which assesses a country’s ability to honor its fi-

nancial commitments, it serves as a central signal for markets, investors and financial institutions. When a country rigorously respects its fiscal rules, it strengthens its financial credibility, reassures the rating agencies and helps maintain its sovereign rating (Gomez-Gonzalez et al., 2022; Hantzsche, 2022; Duygun et al., 2016). This dynamic is particularly crucial, as the government’s rating has a direct influence on the rating of national banks, due to the close link between the solidity of public finances and banking stability. Indeed, banks often hold a significant proportion of government debt in their portfolios. A weakening of the country’s fiscal situation can therefore worsen their exposure to sovereign risk, inciting rating agencies to lower their ratings. This sovereign-bank link creates a potentially vicious circle: a loss of confidence in the government feeds back to the banks, even if their internal management remains prudent. As a result, investment can be curbed, consumption reduced and growth slowed. In this way, fiscal fragility can turn into banking vulnerability, with amplified macroeconomic effects. Conversely, credible fiscal governance, based on clear and respected rules, strengthens sovereign ratings and, by extension, protects the solidity of the banking system. This virtuous circle facilitates external financing, lowers risk premiums and creates a climate of confidence that benefits both banks and the economy as a whole.

Figure 1: Transmission Channels Framework

Source: Authors’ design

3.4 *First views of data linking fiscal rules and bank NPLs: Stylized facts*

In this section, we provide an overview of the data before going on to analyze our main results. To this end, we present descriptive statistics on the correlation between bank

NPLs and the adoption of fiscal rules. We do this in three ways. Firstly, we compare the level of bank NPLs in FR and non-FR countries based on a simple average of our overall sample (Figure 2 left). An analysis of this figure reveals a lower rate of bank NPLs in countries with FR (6.7%) than in non-FR countries (9.2%). Moreover, the difference between the two groups is statistically significant. Secondly, we compare the level of bank NPLs before-after the adoption of fiscal rules (Figure 2 right), inspired by the method of Neuenkirch and Neumeier (2016). The method of Neuenkirch and Neumeier (2016) only takes into account treated units and displays bank NPLs statistics before and after the adoption of fiscal rules, excluding units that have never been treated. The graph shows that despite a higher level of bank NPLs before the adoption of fiscal rules (10.4%), the average level of bank NPLs becomes lower after the adoption of fiscal rules (7.2%).

Figure 2: *This graph presents the average bank NPLs in FR units (country-year with FR adoption) and non-FR units (country-year without FR adoption) from 1990 to 2020.*

Finally, we create a box plot to take into account any limitations of the mean-based comparison (see Figure 3). A closer look at this figure reveals a difference in bank NPLs between countries with and without fiscal rules. Indeed, countries with fiscal rules exceed the median (central line of the box), a 15th (lower hinge of the box) and a 35th (upper hinge of the box) percentile of bank NPLs lower than those without fiscal rules. In fact, these results are justified by the fact that the median line, lower hinge and upper hinge of the box for countries with fiscal rules are respectively lower than those for countries without fiscal rules. Although we obtain graphical evidence through this figure that the adoption of fiscal rules is likely to go hand in hand with bank NPLs, it does not allow

us to assess their magnitude or significance. To avoid overestimating the effect of FR on bank NPLs, we use observations from non-FR countries selected on the basis of the matching procedure as a control group to estimate the counterfactual result.

Figure 3: *Bank nonperforming loans by fiscal rules adoption*

4 Data

We use a panel of 62 developing countries for the period 1990-2020. The choice of this panel data sample is based mainly on our fiscal rules (FR) variable and the availability of data on bank NPLs. On this basis, our sample includes 33 FR countries (*treated group*) and 29 non-FR (*controls group*). The main variables are FR and bank NPLs. We collect information on the existence of a fiscal rule for developing countries from the International Monetary Fund Fiscal Affairs Department Fiscal Policy and Surveillance Division on Fiscal Rules Database, 1985-2021 (Lledó et al., 2017; Schaechter et al., 2012). This dataset assembles information on fiscal rules over the period 1985-2021 for developing countries from publicly available sources to create a dataset.

This dataset contains information⁵ on national and supranational fiscal rules of the fund's member countries. Fiscal rules, as explained above are defined as longer-term

⁵Sources of information: Information is based on fiscal framework laws, published and unpublished country documents, interviews with country officials, staff reports and other IMF papers, information from national authorities, and IMF economists. For EU member countries, information was also drawn from the European Commission's Domestic Fiscal Governance Database, available at http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/db_indicators/fiscal_governance/index_en.htm.

constraints on fiscal policy through numerical limits on fiscal aggregates. Furthermore, the dataset covers four types of rules: **budget balance rules**, **debt rules**, **expenditure rules**, and **revenue rules** that apply to central government, general government, or the public sector. The dataset compiled on fiscal rule may not be comprehensive because some sub-national level rules are not included. There may be a time lag between the implementation date and the effective date of the adopted fiscal rule (Tapsoba, 2012). In fact, the database also includes information on fiscal rules that have been adopted but have not yet gone into effect. However, this is the most comprehensive dataset on fiscal rule for developing countries over a long period. In this paper, we following Tapsoba (2012) in focusing on national fiscal rules because supranational rules usually suffer from the problem of inadequate enforcement and compliance, so that member countries often violate them without sanction. We also draw on the results of Combes et al. (2017), according to which supranational fiscal rules have no significant effect when public debt is high. Moreover by distinguishing the national fiscal rules from the supranational ones, as in Debrun et al. (2008) and Tapsoba (2012), we can explore whether or not the presence of rule-based fiscal policy frameworks at the supranational level influences the treatment effect of national fiscal rules in our empirical analyses. Based on all this information and the existing literature (Combes et al., 2017; 2018; Lledó et al., 2017; Schaechter et al., 2012; Debrun et al., 2008; Sawadogo, 2020; Vinturis, 2022; Tapsoba, 2012; Tapsoba et al., 2012), our treatment variable namely, fiscal rules, will be a dummy variable that takes 1 if country i has established a national fiscal rules at period t and 0 otherwise. Note that the countries adopted the FR on different dates. Thus, countries that adopted later may also constitute controls for those that adopted earlier. This means that the number of FR countries exceeding that of non-FR countries is not a problem.

Outcome variable. Our dependent variable measures the bank non-performing loans, which are the value of NPLs divided by the total value of the loan portfolio (including NPLs before the deduction of specific provisions for loan losses). We use this variable as a proxy for the quality of banks' assets and, more generally, as a proxy for banking system stability. According to Čihák and Schaeck (2010), bank non-performing loans ratio is useful for assessing the quality of a bank's loan portfolio, but it is not sufficient on its own to anticipate banking crises. It functions more effectively as an ex post indicator of deteriorating credit conditions rather than as an early warning signal. Therefore, it should be interpreted as part of a broader set of prudential indicators and incorporated into a multi-indicator framework when evaluating the stability of the banking system.

Main controls/Matching variables. Based on the literature, we select covariates that include structural and institutional indicators. These factors are likely to explain the choice of adopting fiscal rules and bank NPLs in a given country. Consequently, we control for the endogeneity of the following factors: GDP per capita, FDI, public debt, capital openness, total reserves/months, inflation targeting, political stability, and bureaucracy quality.

GDP per capita is a key determinant of a country’s likelihood to adopt fiscal rules. A higher GDP per capita is typically associated with a more advanced level of economic development, which often correlates with stronger institutional capacity, better governance, and an administrative framework capable of managing public finances effectively. In this context, middle- and high-income countries tend to possess the technical and human resources necessary to design, implement, and enforce credible fiscal rules (Schaechter et al., 2012; Eyraud et al., 2018). Additionally, higher per capita income enhances a country’s exposure to international financial markets, increasing the pressure to adopt fiscal discipline mechanisms in order to maintain the confidence of creditors and investors. Overall, a higher GDP per capita facilitates the adoption of fiscal rules by reinforcing both the political incentives for budgetary transparency and the technical capacity for effective rule-based fiscal management.

Higher levels of **Foreign Direct Investment (FDI)** may increase the likelihood of adopting fiscal rules, as governments seek to strengthen credibility with international investors. Fiscal rules act as a commitment mechanism to sound public finance, helping to attract and sustain foreign capital inflows (Debrun et al., 2008; Schaechter et al., 2012). In developing countries, FDI often serves as a catalyst for broader macro-fiscal reforms, including the institutionalization of fiscal discipline (Bova et al., 2015).

Public debt, defined as the total liabilities owed by the government, is a key measure of fiscal sustainability. When debt reaches high levels, it can threaten macroeconomic stability and investor confidence. In response, governments often adopt fiscal rules to restore credibility and commit to long-term debt control (Caselli and Wingender, 2018). Evidence suggests that heavily indebted countries, particularly in emerging markets, are more likely to institutionalize such rules to reassure financial markets (Heinemann et al., 2018).

We then control **capital openness**, i.e. the extent to which a country allows the free movement of financial capital across its borders. A high degree of openness increases exposure to global financial markets and can amplify investor sensitivity to fiscal policy decisions. In such a context, governments may adopt fiscal rules to enhance their policy

credibility and mitigate the risks of capital flight or volatility (Schuknecht et al., 2011).

In addition, we control **total reserves/months**. Total reserves, measured in months of imports, reflect a country’s external liquidity buffer. Higher reserves are often associated with greater macroeconomic stability, which can support the adoption of fiscal rules to formalize prudent fiscal management (Jeanne and Sandri, 2020).

Inflation targeting is a monetary policy framework where central banks commit to maintaining inflation within a specified range. Countries adopting IT often pursue broader macroeconomic credibility, which complements the adoption of fiscal rules to ensure policy consistency and fiscal discipline. Empirical studies suggest that the combination of IT and fiscal rules leads to more disciplined macroeconomic policies than when either is implemented alone. For instance, Combes et al. (2018) find that IT strengthens fiscal performance, and the joint implementation of IT and fiscal rules is associated with improved fiscal outcomes. Similarly, Minea and Tapsoba (2014) highlight that the sequence of adopting IT and fiscal rules matters, with the adoption of IT prior to fiscal rules enhancing fiscal discipline. We take into account this observations by controlling inflation targeting variable.

Regarding the **political stability**, it has been demonstrated that it reduces uncertainty around policy implementation and increases the likelihood of adopting long-term institutional commitments like fiscal rules. Stable political environments are more conducive to rule-based governance, while frequent political turnover or conflict tends to undermine fiscal credibility and reform continuity (Heinemann et al., 2018).

Finally, we control the **bureaucracy quality**. High-quality bureaucracies support the adoption of fiscal rules by ensuring effective rule design, credible enforcement, and continuity in fiscal policy implementation. Countries with strong, independent, and competent public administrations are more likely to institutionalize fiscal rules successfully, as they can manage complex budget processes and resist political pressures (Alesina and Tabellini, 2007; Dabla-Norris et al., 2010).

5 Methodology

The central question we seek to answer is whether the adoption of fiscal rules improves financial–stability in developing countries in the context of the energy transition and rising global energy prices—in fiscal rules countries (treatment group) compared to non-fiscal rules countries (control group). The economic literature suggests that the adoption of fiscal rules is anything but a random feature (see, for instance, Combes et al., 2017;

Sawadogo, 2020; Combes et al., 2018; Tapsoba et al., 2012). It may depend on several factors, including macroeconomic stability, maintaining fiscal sustainability, avoiding negative spillover effects within a monetary union, and ensuring the credibility of government policies over time (Kopits and Symansky, 1998). These factors—which may also affect the financial stability—make financial stability adoption endogenous (not random) through the problem of selection bias⁶. To circumvent this problem and determine the impact of the fiscal rules, we use a newer and more efficient impact assessment method, namely entropy balancing method, which was developed by Hainmueller (2012). In fact, this methodology has been used in many recent impact studies. For example—as part of the fiscal rules. Vinturis (2022) has used it to show how budget rules shape government spending behavior. Apeti et al. (2025) used this method to assess the effect of fiscal rule adoption on public spending efficiency. Sawadogo (2020) has used this technique to assess the effect of fiscal rules on financial market access. Apeti et al. (2024) used it to establish the link between fiscal rule adoption and the reduction of sovereign debt denominated in foreign currencies. As part of other macroeconomic and environmental studies, Balima and Sy (2021) used it to evaluate the effect of IMF programs on sovereign debt crises in 106 developing countries from 1970 to 2016. Coulibaly (2024) has used it to assess the effect of resource-backed loans adoption on ecological efficiency of human development in African countries.

The approach used in this study is based on the principle that fiscal rule adoption is the treatment and financial stability, as measured by nonperforming loans, is the outcome variable. The units of observation are the observations of a country-year. The observations with a fiscal rule are the treatment group and the observations without a fiscal rule are the control group. Treatment effect on treated (ATT) is defined as follows:

$$ATT = E[Y_{(1)}|T=1] - E[Y_0|T=1] \quad (1)$$

where $Y_{(.)}$ is the outcome variable measuring the financial stability. The T indicates whether the observation—unit is subject to fiscal rules adoption ($T = 1$) or not ($T = 0$). $E[(Y_{(1)}|T=1]$ is the financial stability level during the fiscal rules period, $E[(Y_0|T=1)]$ is the counterfactual result for countries that had adopted fiscal rules, i.e. the financial

⁶In fact, treated and untreated countries are not identical, and their differences may therefore act as confounders when affecting their financial stability. Sawadogo (2020), believes that the reasons why developing countries adopt fiscal rules could be related to a country’s macroeconomic conditions and political situation. This raises an endogeneity problem, which he addresses with a matching approach (since conventional linear regressions are not as reliable). We do the same.

stability in countries that had adopted fiscal rules if they had not.

The problem now is that $E[Y(0)|T = 1]$ is not observable because of the non-random nature of fiscal rule adoption. If this were the case, ATT could be easily identified by comparing financial stability in countries with fiscal rules and countries without fiscal rules. While, a good identification of ATT also requires a good approximation of $E[Y(0)|T = 1]$ to avoid a counterfactual problem in the selection. One solution would be to compare the average level of financial stability between countries with and without fiscal rules to get around this difficulty. To do this, we match fiscal rules units with units non-fiscal rules (based on some specific factors) that are as close as possible in terms of observable characteristics that meet two criteria, namely correlation with the adoption of fiscal rules and financial stability. Assuming that the units without fiscal rules are close enough to the units with fiscal rules, any difference in financial stability is attributable to the adoption of fiscal rules (Sawadogo, 2020; Vinturis, 2022). However, this assumption would be ad hoc, since the decision to implement a fiscal rule may depend on some omitted variables (macroeconomic conditions, institutional quality, degree of budgetary vulnerability, political institutions etc.) that also affect financial stability, which would still lead to a self-selection bias (Sawadogo, 2020).

In this case, the estimate of the ATT under unconfoundedness (or conditional independence)⁷. Considering these various elements and proofs, we can rewrite equation 1 as follows:

$$ATT = E[(Y_{(1)}|T=1, X = x) - E[Y_0|T=1, X = x]] \quad (2)$$

where $X = x$ is a vector of observable covariates that may affect both the decision to adopt fiscal rule and the financial stability, $E[Y(1)|T = 1, X = x]$ is the financial stability of fiscal rule units, and $E[Y(0)|T = 0, X = x]$ is the expected financial stability for the synthetic control units. At this point, we can safely estimate ATT using the entropy balancing method, which is a two-step process (Hainmueller, 2012). The first is to compute weights for the control group (non-treated group). In principle, these weights can satisfy given balanced constraints that incorporate sampling moments of observable characteristics (X). we choose balance constraints that prescribe equal mean

⁷Given that there is conditional independence (see for instance Rosenbaum and Rubin (1983); Smith and Todd (2005); Heckman and Singer (2008); Lechner (1999)). Caliendo and Kopeinig (2008) believes that unconfoundedness implies that all factors that influence treatment and outcome must be observed by the researcher.), meaning that systematic differences in outcomes between treated and comparison individuals with the same covariates values are attributable to treatment, we can replace the unobservable term $E[Y(0)|T = 1]$ in equation 1 with the observable term $E[Y(0)|T = 1, X = x]$.

values of the covariates between the treatment and control groups in following [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2016\)](#). In fact, we want to ensure that the control group (in this case Non-fiscal rule countries), on average, has non-treatment units that are as similar as possible to the treated units⁸. The second step uses the weights from the first step in a regression analysis where financial stability measured by nonperforming loans is the dependent variable. Furthermore, in the second step, we control for the covariates employed in the first step. This is equivalent to including control variables in a randomized experiment and increases estimation efficiency. The empirical literature estimates that it is possible to include additional control variables that are used to calculate the weights in the first step. As indicated by [Hainmueller \(2012\)](#) and [Neuenkirch and Neumeier \(2016\)](#), this is similar to including control variables in a randomized experiment and increases the efficiency of the estimation. Moreover, one of the advantages of the entropy balancing method is that time and country-specific effects are taken into account in the second step to account for temporal effects such as the global financial crisis and country-specific heterogeneity resulting, for example, from differences in the political, economic and institutional environment (see, for instance, [Sawadogo, 2020](#); [Vinturis, 2022](#)). Also, entropy balancing allows us to identify the effect of fiscal rule by comparing fiscal rule and non-fiscal rule countries that are similar on observable characteristics while taking care to account for country- and time-specific effects (see, for instance, [Apeti et al., 2024](#); [Apeti et al., 2025](#); [Vinturis, 2022](#); [Sawadogo, 2020](#)). Indeed, the literature reveals that entropy balancing has several advantages over traditional matching methods ([Neuenkirch and Neumeier, 2016](#)). Moreover, recall that a particularly important advantage is that entropy balancing is nonparametric, i.e., it is not necessary to specify an empirical model for the outcome variable or selection in the treatment. Basically, treatment effect estimates based on entropy balancing do not suffer from multicollinearity because the reweighting scheme orthogonalizes the covariates with respect to the treatment indicator. Unlike standard regression analyses. Also, entropy balancing ensures a sufficient balance of pretreatment characteristics between treatment and control groups, even with a small sample or a limited number of untreated units. This makes it possible to construct an appropriate control group that is a near-perfect counterfactual of the treated group. Moreover, with classical matching methods, e.g. propensity score matching, nearest-neighbor matching, each untreated unit receives either a weight of 0 if it is not a better match to a treated

⁸In the context of our study, this procedure ensures that once the weights are generated, fiscal rule and non-fiscal rule countries exhibit similar trends in their outcome variable over the pre-treatment period (see, e.g, [Ogrokhina and Rodriguez \(2019\)](#) on the case of inflation targeting).

unit, or a weight of 1 if it is a better match to a treated unit while the entropy balancing method guarantees a high balance of covariates between the treatment and control groups, even in small samples, allowing us to construct a suitable control group representing a near perfect counterfactual of the treated group.

Finally, by combining reweighting with regression analysis, entropy balancing allows us to treat the panel structure of our data appropriately. Moreover, in the second step of the matching approach, i.e., in the regression analysis, we can control for both country and time fixed effects. The inclusion of country fixed effects is particularly useful to account for potential unobserved heterogeneity between countries that have never adopted fiscal rule and those that have, as the economic, political environments and macroeconomic conditions of these two groups of countries may differ beyond the covariates used in the entropy balancing approach ([Sawadogo, 2020](#)). By including country fixed effects, we also control for time-invariant country-specific factors that could lead to differences in financial stability across countries. In other words, by including country fixed effects, we can control for country-specific characteristics that may affect fiscal rule adoption or consumption volatility across countries in the sample. Indeed, entropy balancing may fail to control for potential endogeneity biases due to unobserved time-varying factors that may affect both fiscal rule and financial stability, as well as the reverse causality problem that may exist between the treatment variable and the outcome variable, and cannot successfully address the inertia of financial stability. This can lead to potentially biased results. For this reason, we complement entropy balancing with series alternative estimation methods in the robustness section.

6 Empirical results

6.1 Results from covariates balance

In Table 1 panel A, we present the sample means of all matching variables for the FR (column 1) and non-FR (column 2) groups. Next, we report the differences in means between these groups with the level of significance (p-value) in column [3], and finally the t-statistics in column [4]. Our data reveal that periods in which fiscal rules are in place differ from periods in which there are no fiscal rules in place for almost all the relevant pre-treatment factors selected. We note that the political situation and macroeconomic conditions are better in countries with fiscal rules than in those without. Indeed, countries with fiscal rules experience high economic growth, which is in line with the findings of [Afonso and Jalles \(2013\)](#) and [Castro \(2011\)](#). We also note that countries with a fiscal rule are highly attractive to FDI. This result is not surprising, as the implementation of an effective fiscal rule ensures stability, predictability and sustainability of fiscal policies, which in turn fosters an adequate business environment for investors (see [Mitsi, 2023](#)). In addition, countries with fiscal rules have low levels of public debt and high reserves. Several studies have shown that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces public debt. A recent study conducted by [Apeti et al. \(2024\)](#) showed that fiscal rules reduce debt denominated in foreign currency in developing countries. Finally, countries with fiscal rules have high political stability, high bureaucracy quality, a high probability of adopting inflation targeting and low capital openness.

Given these descriptive statistics it is crucial to select an adequate control group before estimating the treatment effect when we use matching approach. Otherwise, the estimated treatment effect of fiscal rule on bank NPLs might be biased. To avoid such an error, we construct a synthetic control group and compare the sample means of all matching covariates between the treatment group (column 2) and this synthetic control group in panel B. The differences in means between these two groups are statistically insignificant. In fact, entropy balancing provides a perfect control group for our treated units. The synthetic group can therefore be considered an “almost perfect” counterfactual of the treated group, thus resolving potential selection bias due to the adoption of fiscal rules. In other words, the analysis of the two groups in this panel B reveals the effectiveness of entropy balancing, as the difference shown in panel A seems to disappear in panel B.

Table 1: Covariates balance

Panel A: Before weighting	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]	[4]
	FR	Non-FR	Difference	t-Test
Lag GDP per capita	2.5842	2.3317	-0,2525	-0.925
Lag FDI	4.1141	3.2163	-0.8978***	-3.814
Public debt	52.8503	54.6785	1.8282	0.998
Capital openness	0.2616	0.8323	0.5707***	-15.560
Reserves/months	4.9013	4.4817	-0.4196**	-2.557
Inflation targeting	0.3243	0.3219	-0.0024	-0.104
Political stability	0.5594	0.5053	-0.0541***	-7.535
Bureaucracy quality	2.3394	1.7508	-0.5886***	-13.144
<i>Observations</i>	<i>386</i>	<i>622</i>		
Panel B: After weighting	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]	[4]
	FR	Non-FR	Difference	t-Test
Lag GDP per capita	2.297	2.297	0.000	0.1
Lag FDI	4.139	4.139	0.000	7.9
Public debt	52.31	52.31	0.000	1.1
Capital openness	0.83	0.83	0.000	114.0
Reserves/months	4.75	4.75	0.000	1.3
Inflation targeting	0.3523	0.3523	0.000	5.0
Political stability	0.5519	0.5519	0.000	44.4
Bureaucracy quality	2.413	2.413	0.000	158.1
<i>Observations</i>	<i>386</i>	<i>622</i>		
<i>Total of weights</i>	<i>386</i>	<i>386</i>		

Note: Panel A presents the pre-weighting sample means of the matching covariates for country-year observations where FR were in place (the treatment group) in column [2] and country-year observations where no FR were in place (the potential control group) in column [1] while panel B presents the sample means matching covariates after weighting across the treated group and the synthetic control group obtained from entropy balancing. ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1

6.2 Main results

Based on synthetic controls in Table 1 panel B, we estimate the effect of fiscal rules adoption on NPLs (ATT) in developing countries using weighted least squares method. This brings us back to estimating the equation for the second step:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta FR_{it} + \gamma X_{it} + \nu_i + \theta_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (3)$$

where Y_{it} is the bank NPLs of country i in year t . FR_{it} is a dummy variable equal to 1 for a country i that has adopted a fiscal rule in year t , and 0 otherwise. X_{it} is the set of covariates described in Section 4. The ν_i and θ_t represent country- and time-fixed effects, respectively, capturing unobserved heterogeneity. Finally, ϵ_{it} is the term for idiosyncratic error. The results are reported in Table 2. Columns [1]-[4] present the second-stage results with no addition of the covariates used in the first stage in constructing the synthetic group. Column [1] excludes country- and year-fixed effects. Columns [2]-[3] include respectively country- and time-fixed effects while column [4] includes these two effects jointly. Finally, columns [5]-[8] repeat the exercise of columns [1]-[4] except for adding in each second stage regression the covariates used in the first stage, namely lag GDP per capita, lag FDI, public debt, capital openness, reserve/months, inflation targeting, political stability, and bureaucracy quality. It is useful to note that including matching covariates in the second stage of entropy balancing increases the quality of the matching (as in a randomized experiment), while controlling for country- and year-fixed effects eliminates any country- or year-specific effects. The results of these specifications show that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces bank NPLs in the countries in our sample. This result ranges from -0.3837 percentage points (column [3]) to -1.7799 percentage points (column [8]) — a robust result given the relative stability of the coefficients in the eight (8) specifications in the Table 2, with an average effect of -0.97 percentage points. In other words, the adoption of fiscal rules reduces bank NPLs by an average of 0.97 percentage points in countries with fiscal rules compared with countries without fiscal rules.

These results could be explained by the effect of macroeconomic factors influencing bank NPLs. Indeed, fiscal rules promote budgetary discipline by reducing the primary deficit and improving the overall budget balance (Combes et al., 2018; Caselli and Reynaud, 2020; Caselli and Wingender, 2021), which in turn improves the expansion phase

of the economy. While the expansion phase is characterized by relatively low bank NPLs, insofar as consumers and businesses have sufficient income and revenue streams to service their debts (Dimitrios et al., 2016). As a result, fiscal rules end up reducing commercial banks' nonperforming loans. In the same vein, the adoption of fiscal rules could improve the economic cycle of adopting countries and reduce bank NPLs. In addition, fiscal rules, by helping to avoid budget debauchery (Sawadogo, 2020), improve GDP growth, which in turn reduces the bank NPLs induced by the rapid transmission of macroeconomic evolution's and the ability of economic agents, notably the governments and firms, to service their loans (Bangia et al., 2002; Carey, 2002).

The recent financial crisis has established a theoretical and empirical link between sovereign debt crises and banking crises. According to Reinhart and Rogoff (2011), there is ample empirical evidence that banking crises most often precede or coincide with sovereign debt crises. Sovereign debt crises reduce fiscal space and the government's ability to meet its borrowings. The deterioration of public finances places a "ceiling" on the market's assessment of the credibility of national banks and, as a result, banks find themselves short of liquidity (Reinhart and Rogoff, 2011). As a result, banks are forced to reduce their lending, and debtors are unable to refinance their debts. Furthermore, an increase in public debt may lead to fiscal measures, including cuts in social spending and in the wage component of public consumption (Perotti, 1996). In this context, the adoption of fiscal rules will oblige the government to exercise fiscal prudence and avoid policy mistakes that could jeopardize its solvency. Moreover, it is widely recognized in the literature that fiscal rules are generally designed to correct the incentives of policy-makers to overspend, particularly in good times, in order to ensure fiscal responsibility and debt sustainability. For example, Asatryan et al. (2018) have shown that the adoption of fiscal rules promotes fiscal discipline by reducing the debt-to-GDP ratio and lowering the probability of a debt crisis. By avoiding debt defaults, fiscal rules help countries to meet repayment of their debts held with national banks. Similarly, the adoption of fiscal rules requires countries to cap deficits, debts and public spending, which are seen as a means of discouraging fiscal profligacy (Eyraud et al., 2018). Consequently, fiscal rules, by improving budgetary discipline through sovereign debt reduction (Mineea et al., 2021; Asatryan et al., 2018; Apeti et al., 2024), for example, avoid budgetary and banking crises, which are closely linked. This ultimately has a negative impact on nonperforming loans. These results show that fiscal rules, side from its acknowledged benefits for fiscal policy goals, appear as an efficient tool to strengthen monetary policy in developing countries more stable banking systems.

Fiscal rules, through their ability to limit the accumulation of public arrears, have a major impact on banking sector stability, notably through the reduction of non-performing loans. Payment arrears—unpaid government debts beyond their due date - are a source of fragility when it comes to companies, particularly those that depend on government contracts, especially in low-income countries (IMF, 2021; Cebotari et al., 2021). By affecting their cash flow, these delays reduce their ability to repay bank loans, leading to an increase in NPLs on bank balance sheets. This phenomenon is particularly acute in low-income countries, where the absence of strict rules, poor budget planning and ineffective cash management regularly fuel the formation of arrears. Thus, weaknesses in budget management are not limited to a public finance problem: they are transmitted directly to the banking system via the growing insolvency of the private sector exposed to the State. Mechanisms such as structural balance rules, expenditure ceilings and automatic warning and correction mechanisms not only help stabilize public finances, but also anticipate and avoid chronic under-budgeting of certain vulnerable expenditure areas, such as salaries or payments to suppliers. By preventing unfunded commitments and forcing better cash management, these rules reduce the use of arrears as an informal budget adjustment tool. The positive effects on banking stability through non-performing loans can be significant. Lower arrears mean better creditworthiness for companies exposed to public procurement, which in turn improves the quality of banks' credit portfolios. As a result, banks see their level of delinquency decrease, their provisioning requirements fall and their ability to grant new loans increase. In turn, this boosts investor confidence in the banking system, consolidating financial stability as a whole. In concrete cases in Africa, such as Ghana, Niger and Senegal, the adoption of sound fiscal rules has reduced arrears, improved corporate liquidity and cut the volume of non-performing loans (IMF, 2021). This fiscal-financial link forms a virtuous loop: better fiscal governance alleviates pressure on the banking sector, and contributes to more balanced and sustainable growth.

Very strong evidence has been found that fiscal rules improve the public spending efficiency in developing country (see Apeti et al., 2025). This means that fiscal rules, by increasing the efficiency of public spending, can reduce bank NPLs in a number of ways. First, by stimulating economic growth, a better allocation of public spending will boost productive public investment (infrastructure, education, health), thereby improving the economy's competitiveness. A more dynamic economy means more income for companies and households, which in turn means greater credit repayment capacity. As a result, there are fewer defaults, reinforcing banking stability. Second, targeted support for vulnerable sectors. By directing spending towards troubled but viable sectors, the government can

avoid massive bankruptcies and defaults. For example: granting agricultural subsidies during droughts, aid to SMEs in times of economic crisis. This significantly reduces bank NPLs. Third, strengthening macroeconomic stability. As explained above, fiscal rules guarantee good macroeconomic stability. In fact, well-managed public finances via fiscal reform reduce the risk of fiscal or monetary instability (inflation, devaluation, etc.), creating a predictable environment and reducing the risk of default by borrowers affected by economic volatility. Fourth, fiscal rules reduce bank NPLs by improving public services through better use of public spending. In fact, if the government efficiently provides education, health or transport, households don't have to go into debt to compensate for these deficiencies. This improves their financial health, and therefore their ability to service their bank debts. Finally, the last channel is that of reducing unemployment/income inequality. When public spending is effectively employed to finance job-creating projects, it reduces the unemployment rate and increases household incomes, negatively affecting payment defaults. This reduces bank NPLs and ensures strong banking stability.

Table 2: Fiscal rules and bank non-performing loans—Baseline results

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
VARIABLES								
FR dummy	-0.3907*** (0.0576)	-1.4029*** (0.2506)	-0.3837*** (0.0561)	-1.4410*** (0.2163)	-0.4052*** (0.0653)	-1.5730*** (0.3966)	-0.3955*** (0.0618)	-1.7799*** (0.3564)
Constant	1.8305*** (0.0337)	2.3017*** (0.1711)	2.2544*** (0.2045)	2.7870*** (0.2100)	2.1537*** (0.1465)	2.2415*** (0.4246)	2.8279*** (0.2306)	3.9235*** (0.5338)
Covariates	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year/FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144	774	774	774	774
R-squared	0.0441	0.5379	0.1270	0.6104	0.3474	0.6796	0.4240	0.7524

This table presents the causal impact of fiscal rules on nonperforming loans obtained by weighted least squares regressions. Robust standard errors are in parentheses ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

7 Robustness checks

Our estimates show that the adoption of fiscal rules have significantly and negative effect on bank non-performing loans. In this section, we test the robustness of these results with the aim of strengthening our confidence.

7.1 *Alternative estimation methods*

Propensity score matching estimates (PSM). We begin our robustness checks exercise with a impact analysis method, PSM. As explained above, the adoption of fiscal rules is probably not a random event. For example, the adoption of fiscal rules may be correlated with an economic crisis (see, for instance, [Combes et al., 2017](#); [Sawadogo, 2020](#); [Eyraud et al., 2018](#), etc.). We therefore use another method, like our baseline model, to transform the adoption of the fiscal rules into a quasi-experimental event, and thus estimate the effect of the treatment of the adoption of the fiscal rules on nonperforming loans. To this end, we rely on the popular impact evaluation method Propensity Scores Matching (PSM), which comprises two steps: firstly, propensity scores (PS) are estimated using the logit or probit method; secondly, these PS are used to match treated and untreated observations, and thus calculate the treatment effect of fiscal rules adoption, i.e. the average treatment effect on treated (ATT). These observable characteristics are summarized in a propensity score (PS) which indicates the probability of a country adopt fiscal rules (treatment group), subject to the observable characteristics ([Rosenbaum and Rubin, 1983](#); [Smith and Todd, 2005](#); [Dehejia and Wahba, 2002](#); [Coulibaly, 2025](#)). The propensity score is then used to determine a group of countries that have not adopted fiscal rules (control group). This group of countries serves as a counterfactual for the treatment group. Indeed, assuming that the determinants of nonperforming loans are statistically independent of the fiscal rules adoption, given the common characteristics between the treatment and control groups, the difference in outcome between the two groups, the average effect of treatment on treated (ATT), is attributable to the fiscal rules adoption.

In the second stage, we use various matching algorithms for country matching to test the robustness of our results. In addition, the matching techniques used include nearest-neighbor matching with replacement, which associates each treated country with the n control countries with the closest PS ($n = 1$, $n = 2$ and $n = 3$; are considered). Next, radius matching is also used to match the FRs country to non-FRs countries whose PS lies within a radius of length r (we consider a radius $r = 0.045$, a medium radius $r = 0.09$ and a narrow radius $r = 0.18$). We also follow [Fan \(1993\)](#) and [Heckman et al. \(1998\)](#) in using regression-adjusted local linear matching to couple covariate-adjusted results for the treatment group with corresponding covariate-adjusted results for the control group using local linear regression weights. Finally, we use kernel matching as a matching algorithm to associate a treated country with all control countries, weighted proportionally to their

proximity in terms of PS to the treated country. In Table 3 panel A, we present the results of the new ATTs while the results of the propensity score estimation are presented in Table 4, column [1]. We can see that all coefficients are stable, confirming the negative effect of fiscal rule on bank NPLs.

Endogenous switching regression. Second, we re-estimate our main model using endogenous switching regression models are estimated. The endogenous switching regression model is used to deal with situations where individuals (or observation units) self-select into different “regimes”, and where this selection is correlated with observed outcomes (see Nonvide, 2023; Maddala, 1983; Di Falco et al., 2011; Lee and Trost, 1978; Asfaw et al., 2012; Carter and Milon, 2005; Nonvide, 2019). Following Nonvide (2023); Di Falco et al. (2011); Nonvide (2019) and Asfaw et al. (2012), we use this model to compare the expected bank NPLs of adopters of fiscal rules (a) versus non-adopters (b), and to examine the expected bank NPLs in the counterfactual hypothetical cases where adopters have not adopted (c), and where non-adopters have adopted (d). The advantage of this model is that it effectively corrects for selection bias, i.e. units are not randomly assigned to a "regime" (i.e. adopt and non-adopt). In addition, it makes it possible to compare results between "regimes". In fact, the model makes it possible to estimate counterfactuals: what would have been the outcome for those who adopted the fiscal rule if they had not adopted the fiscal rule, and vice versa. We use adoption in the neighboring country to instrument the fiscal rule in the estimation of the equation in the first step. Then we perform a prediction to obtain the treatment effects. Table 3, panel B, shows the coefficients of bank NPLs expected under actual and counterfactual conditions. The results in cells (a) and (b) show a positive difference. The treatment effect seems high in countries with fiscal rule. On the basis of this simple comparison, it could be misleading to attribute the difference in bank NPLs to the simple adoption of fiscal rule by countries. We must confuse this result with a counterfactual situation. In the case of *counterfactual (c)*, it is clear that the treatment effect for countries adopting fiscal rule is 0.72. This equates to a difference of around 95% in bank NPLs on average (the formula is $100*(e^{ATT} - 1)$, see Asfaw et al., 2012). This means that if the countries that adopted the fiscal rule had not done so, their bank NPLs would have increased by 95%. In the case of *counterfactual (d)*, if non-FR countries had adopted the reform, their bank NPLs would have decreased by 43%. Finally, the effect of transitional heterogeneity is positive, implying that the effect of fiscal rule on bank NPLs is significantly stronger for countries that have actually adopted FR than for non-FR.

OLS estimates. Third, we test the robustness of our results using the Ordinary

Least Squares (OLS). The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) estimator is a common rule for calculating estimates of linear regression coefficients. This estimator is relatively simple, but nevertheless possesses a number of desirable special properties, such as, under appropriate conditions, being the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE). Results reported in column [4] of Table 4 suggest a negative and significant effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs, with a magnitude of about 0.31 percentage points, qualitatively comparable to that of the baseline results (0.81 percentage points).

System-GMM estimates. Fourth, we treat any endogeneity that could affect our results using the two-step system-GMM dynamic panel estimator proposed by [Blundell and Bond \(1998\)](#). The strength of this method is that it allows us to control for the persistence of monetary results, in particular bank crises, bank NPLs and provisions to bank NPLs; to control for the Nickell bias ([Nickell, 1981](#)) that appears in a dynamic panel model, a model with lagged endogenous control variables and fixed effects, to limit the influence of unobservable time-varying factors that can influence both outcome and treatment variables, notably the moral hazard of borrowers at banks, and to alleviate the difficulty of finding an exogenous instrument to estimate the effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs. As a result, this method offers us the possibility of instrumenting other potentially endogenous explanatory variables in addition to the main regressor, which is endogenous. The new results are presented in column [6] of Table 4. In fact, these results lead to conclusions that are qualitatively similar to the baseline results. In addition, looking at the instrument selection criteria, the Hansen test does not reject the hypothesis of instrument validity. Finally, the AR (1) test for the absence of autocorrelation of the first-order error term and the AR (2) test for the absence of autocorrelation of the second-order error term do not raise concerns about the validity of our estimates.

IV estimates. Finally, we present the results of our regressions with external instruments in addition to robustness checks with internal instruments to mitigate the endogeneity problem of fiscal rules adoption. The proportion of neighboring countries adopting fiscal rules is expected to affect policy adoption in the host country, but not to have a direct effect on bank NPLs. With this first instrument, the proportion of neighboring countries adopting fiscal rules can be subdivided into two. The first is the inverse of the weighting matrix for the geographical distance between (distance), while the second is taken to be the number of fiscal rules in place in countries sharing borders with the country of interest (Contiguity). Indeed, the adoption of fiscal rules in several neighboring countries is likely to increase the probability of adopting the same policy, for example due to the imitation effect of adopting common policies in developing countries. The

main idea behind this instrument is that reforms in neighboring countries can influence the adoption of national reforms, given that they are geographically linked, as **Waldo Tobler's** law puts it, for example through peer pressure or an imitation effect to send a signal of credibility on international markets (Balvir, 2023). We are not the first to use this instrument in the literature. Indeed, a number of recent studies have used it as an external instrument to instrument the adoption of fiscal rules. For instance, Ardanaz et al. (2021) use it to address the endogeneity of flexible rules. Similarly, Caselli and Reynaud (2020) use it as a new instrument to address the potential endogeneity problem of fiscal rules. The formula is given by equation 4 below:

$$Contiguity_IV_{it} = \sum_{j \neq i}^{n-1} FR_{j,t} * X_{j,i,t} \quad (4)$$

with j the neighboring country of domestic country i . $FR_{j,t}$ is a dummy variable taking a value 1 when country j has a fiscal rule at time t , and 0 if country j does not have a fiscal rule. $X_{j,i,t}$ takes the value 0 when countries have no common borders and sum the number of countries with common borders. Finally, $Contiguity_IV_{it}$ captures the number of fiscal rules in place in countries with common borders with respect to the domestic economy. Unlike studies that use only contiguity as an instrument, we use contiguity and reinforce the robustness of results by using idistance as an instrument for several reasons. The first reason is that in the adjacency matrix, islands have no neighbors, i.e. countries whose borders are separated by islands obtain 0 as value in the matrix. Secondly, as our dataset is not complete, some countries may have no neighbors, which can lead to inconsistencies since it would appear that the two spatial entities have no common border. Algebraically, after normalization, the w_{ij} weights of the geographic distance weighting matrix are given as follows:

$$W_{ij} = \begin{cases} \frac{1/d_{ij}}{\sum_j 1/d_{ij}}, & \text{for } i \neq j \\ 0, & \text{for } i = j \end{cases}$$

Where d_{ij} is the Euclidian distance between the capital of country i and country j for $i \neq j$. To finish, given that the fiscal rules were adopted with the aim of consolidating the budget, i.e. limiting by example sovereign debt defaults and debt restructuring (Debrun and Kumar, 2007; Combes et al., 2017; Tapsoba, 2012; Kumar et al., 2009; Schaechter et al., 2012; Ayuso-i Casals et al., 2009; Bova et al., 2014; Guerguil et al., 2017; Aghion et al., 2007). So, sovereign debt default and restructuring can be a good (but not perfect) instrument for adopting fiscal rules. The results of the first stage presented in Table 4, columns [2]-[3], show a strong correlation between our instruments and the probability of

adopting a fiscal rule: the fact that neighboring countries adopt a fiscal rule increases the probability of adopting the reform in the neighboring country by around 0.28 percentage points (contiguity) and 3.94 percentage points (distance), suggesting that the instrumental variable strategy is relevant. At the same time, the Stock-Wright p-value indicates that the results are not affected by a weak instrument problem. Using the instruments of geographical contiguity, inverse of geographical distance, and lagged fiscal rule as instruments, we observe a high amplitude of fiscal rule on bank NPLs, up to 2.69 percentage points. These results are in line with our baseline estimates (see, Table 3), having a fiscal rule neutralizes the rise in bank NPLs during fiscal consolidations (see, Table 4, columns [5]). The resulting estimated marginal effect of fiscal consolidation in countries with fiscal rules is not statistically different from zero. In summary, although it is difficult to establish an unequivocal causal link in this context, the results of Approach IV-2SLS are consistent with the benchmark findings, suggesting that fiscal rules are effective even after potential endogeneity concerns are explicitly taken into account.

Table 3: Fiscal rule and bank NPLs—Robustness check

Panel A : Propensity score matching	1-Nearest Neighbor	2-Nearest Neighbor	3-Nearest Neighbor	Radius Matching			Local linear regression	Kernel
	Matching			r=0.005	r=0.05	r=0.01	Matching	Matching
ATT	-0.3452*** (0.1158)	-0.2689*** (0.0983)	-0.2741*** (0.1010)	-0.3010*** (0.0661)	-0.2915*** (0.0784)	-0.3330*** (0.0634)	-0.2758*** (0.0830)	-0.2833*** (0.0610)
Observations	814	814	814	814	814	814	814	814
Treated	261	261	261	261	261	261	261	261
Untreated	552	552	552	552	552	552	552	552
Panel B: Endogenous switching regression	<i>Decision stage</i>		<i>Treatments effects</i>					
	FR adopters		FR non-adopters					
	(a)	(c)						
FR adopters	0.72*** (0.0337)	0.05*** (0.0073)	ATT = 0.67*** (0.0264)					
	(d)	(b)						
FR non-adopters	0.75*** (0.0368)	0.39*** (0.0216)	TU = 0.36*** (0.0152)					
Heterogeneity effects	BH0=-0.03	BH1=-0.34	TH=0.31					
Panel C: Alternative definition of bank NPLs	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
FR dummy	-0.1922** (0.0756)	-1.1738*** (0.2965)	-0.2685*** (0.0605)	-1.3150*** (0.2757)	-0.2226*** (0.0622)	-1.0493*** (0.3918)	-0.2867*** (0.0529)	-1.5763*** (0.3021)
Constant	1.6030*** (0.0553)	2.3272*** (0.1908)	2.3897*** (0.1775)	3.2307*** (0.2658)	2.3853*** (0.1856)	2.8547*** (0.4918)	3.1800*** (0.2176)	4.0412*** (0.5014)
Main controls	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year/FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	814	814	814	814	814	814	814	814
R-squared	0.0130	0.4365	0.2663	0.6817	0.2590	0.5853	0.4339	0.7436

Note:(a) and (b) represent observed expected bank NPLs per country; (c) and (d) represent counterfactual expected bank NPLs per country. ATT = the effect of the treatment on the treated. TU = the effect of the treatment on the untreated. BH = the effect of base heterogeneity for adopters, and non-adopters. TH = (TT-TU), i.e., transitional heterogeneity. Standard errors are in parentheses. *** p < 0.01, ** p < 0.05, * p < 0.1.

Table 4: Fiscal rule and bank NPLs—Robustness check

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]
	<i>PS</i>	<i>Fisrt step of IV-2SLS</i>		<i>OLS</i>	<i>IV-2SLS</i>	<i>GMM system</i>
VARIABLES	<i>FR</i>	<i>FR</i>		<i>Bank NPLs</i>	<i>Bank NPLs</i>	<i>Bank NPLs</i>
Lag bank NPLs						0.1140*** (0.0419)
FR dummy				-0.3121*** (0.0613)	-2.6886*** (0.3257)	-1.3755*** (0.3687)
Lag GDP per capita	-0.0370*** (0.0140)	-0.0288** (0.0137)	-0.0087 (0.0152)	-0.0408*** (0.0088)	-0.0372*** (0.0073)	-0.0143*** (0.0045)
Lag FDI	-0.0361*** (0.0135)	-0.0307** (0.0142)	-0.0476** (0.0225)	0.0057 (0.0078)	0.0229** (0.0110)	-0.0055 (0.0092)
Public debt	-0.0135*** (0.0021)	-0.0107*** (0.0021)	-0.0182*** (0.0029)	0.0105*** (0.0010)	0.0113*** (0.0020)	0.0200*** (0.0020)
Capital openness	-0.0365 (0.0324)	-0.0842*** (0.0323)	0.1762*** (0.0461)	-0.1709*** (0.0211)	0.1878*** (0.0270)	0.2653*** (0.0716)
Reserves/months	0.1338*** (0.0154)	0.1077*** (0.0170)	0.0427* (0.0239)	-0.0306*** (0.0102)	-0.0077 (0.0103)	0.0471*** (0.0132)
Inflation targeting	0.6085*** (0.0943)	0.5678*** (0.0973)	0.0747 (0.1337)	-0.0090 (0.0602)	1.1659*** (0.3334)	0.7824** (0.3916)
Political stability	0.3616 (0.3760)	0.2129 (0.3919)	-0.0775 (0.5001)	-0.5728*** (0.1999)	-0.4399 (0.4301)	-1.1274* (0.6295)
Bureaucracy quality	0.2462*** (0.0720)	0.2541*** (0.0714)	0.6743*** (0.0976)	-0.0995** (0.0478)	0.3838* (0.2146)	-0.1712 (0.2848)
<i>idistance</i>		3.9449*** (0.4002)				
<i>contiguity</i>			0.2794*** (0.0508)			
Constant	-1.3065*** (0.2432)	-2.3351*** (0.2849)	-1.0225*** (0.3562)	2.0916*** (0.1449)	1.9844*** (0.5827)	1.0136 (0.9824)
Observations	1,008	1,008	560	814	460	542
Number of instruments					3	37
Number of countries						44
AR(1) test, p-value						0.091
AR(2) test, p-value						0.323
Sargan, p-value						0.000
Hansen, p-value					0.9434	0.654
R-squared				0.2928	0.7776	

Robust standard errors are in brackets. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

7.2 *Alternative dependent variable: banking vulnerability index*

In this section, we extend the definition of our dependent variable by taking into account other banking vulnerability variables. Given that there is no universally accepted empirical measure of banking sector vulnerability in the literature, we choose four variables to measure it: Z-score, capital-to-asset ratio, credit-to-deposit ratio, and credit volatility. We use the Z-score variable for several reasons. First, it is a variable that captures the number of standard deviations that a bank's yield must fall below its expected value to wipe out all the bank's equity and make it insolvent. Secondly, it is inversely related to

the probability of a bank becoming insolvent. The Z-score is defined as $Z = (k + \mu)/\sigma$, where k is share capital as a percentage of assets, μ is return as a percentage of assets, and σ is the standard deviation of return on assets as an indicator of the volatility of returns. Thirdly, it is based on a comparison between banks' reserves in the form of their capitalization and returns, and their risks in the form of the volatility of returns. Finally, as our aim is to relate as closely as possible to the stability of the banking system, this is a fairly relevant variable for our analysis, and also widely used in the literature to apprehend the solvency of the banking system (see [Beck et al., 2010](#); [Claessens and Laeven, 2004](#); [Levieuge et al., 2019](#)). Next, we use the capital-to-asset ratio as an indicator of the vulnerability of the banking system. It simply measures the capitalization of the banking system. According to [Levieuge et al. \(2019\)](#), a higher ratio of this variable indicates a better-capitalized banking system. Then we consider credit-to-deposit ratio. It is designed to measure the magnitude of the credit cycle, as the deviation of credit from the normal range of historical experience, and then to capture excess credit growth. According to [Schularick and Taylor \(2012\)](#), credit growth is effective in providing a leading signal of banking distress. Finally, we credit volatility, which is the volatility of domestic credit to the private sector. Higher credit volatility leads to a sharp fall in the financial resources provided to the private sector by financial companies, for example in the form of loans, purchases of non-equity securities, trade credits and other accounts receivable. This variable is calculated as a five-year moving variance of the credit to private sector by banks (% of GDP).

We use these four variables to calculate a composite banking vulnerability index using the method of [Anderson \(2008\)](#)⁹. We then use it as a dependent variable to run the regressions in equation 3. The results presented in the columns of Table 3 [1]-[8], show that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces the vulnerability of the banking system, thus promoting the solidity and stability of the banking system.

7.3 Accounting for additional control variables and alternative samples

We further extend our main specification by including additional covariates. In fact, NPLs of banks are likely to impede economic growth and reduce economic efficiency. At the same time, shocks to the financial system may originate from bank-specific factors or

⁹[Coulibaly \(2024\)](#) used this technique in its study. The reader can refer to this study for more details on the method.

macroeconomic conditions. Several studies have confirmed that macroeconomic conditions affect credit risk (e.g, [Brownbridge et al., 1998](#); [Janzen et al., 2018](#); [Das and Ghosh, 2007](#); [Al-Smadi and Ahmad, 2009](#); etc.). We take all these considerations into account by controlling numerous macroeconomic and institutional variables. We group them into two categories. The macroeconomic category includes broad money growth, fiscal balance, primary balance, bank concentration, debt service total, bank Z score, deposit money banks, unemployment rate, and financial development. while the institutional category includes government effectiveness, control of corruption, and the rule of law. It should be noted that each of these variables has a different influence on bank NPLs. For example, broad money growth can trigger inflation, which in turn is supposed to improve loan repayment by making it cheaper ([Al-Smadi and Ahmad, 2009](#); [Quagliariello, 2007](#)). In the same vein, rising unemployment can negatively influence household cash flows and increase debt burdens. In terms of companies, rising unemployment can signal a drop in production due to a fall in effective demand, leading to lower revenues and a weakening of debt. However, fiscal balance can affect NPLs of banks in ambiguous ways, for example when expansionary fiscal policy mitigates / aggravates the NPL problem ([Dimitrios et al., 2016](#)). The argument used for fiscal balance also prevails for primary balance. The new results reported in Table 5, panel A columns ([1]-[12]) confirm the negative and meaningful impact of fiscal rules on bank nonperforming loans. In panel B, columns [1]-[7], we perform a few additional tests by re-estimating our main model from alternative samples. First, we follow [Reinhart and Rogoff \(2004\)](#) in excluding from the sample any episodes of hyperinflation, i.e. years when the inflation rate was 40% or more. Second, we leave out the years of the financial crisis (2008-2009), during which many countries experienced disruptions and upsets to their fiscal balances. Third, we exclude from our sample the observations during which many countries experienced a banking crisis because of the threats it poses to the economy in general and to the banking system in particular ([Reinhart and Rogoff, 2011](#)). Fourth, we exclude years in which countries with fiscal rules experienced particular economic dynamics, such as currency crises, inflation crises, and systemic crises. Finally, we exclude countries where fiscal rules have recently been adopted because of the potential time lag between reforms and their expected effects. The results of these tests demonstrate the consistency of our findings with these different specifications.

Table 5: Sample modification and adding control variables

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	
Panel A: Adding control variables	Broad money growth	Fiscal balance	Primary balance	Bank concentration	Debt service total	Bank Z score	
FR dummy	-2.0505*** (0.3388)	-1.7920*** (0.3543)	-1.7904*** (0.3544)	-1.8769*** (0.3808)	-0.4608* (0.2752)	-1.8850*** (0.3738)	
Constant	4.5647*** (0.5168)	3.8548*** (0.5316)	3.8725*** (0.5308)	3.7630*** (0.5765)	4.5468*** (0.5614)	3.8387*** (0.5676)	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	691	774	773	692	599	690	
R-squared	0.7625	0.7540	0.7535	0.7652	0.7535	0.7708	
	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]	[11]	[12]	
	Deposit money banks	Unemployment rate	Financial development	Government effectiveness	Control of corruption	Rule of law	
FR dummy	-1.8590*** (0.3780)	-2.0895*** (0.3328)	-2.0270*** (0.3631)	-1.6202*** (0.3908)	-1.2293*** (0.4495)	-1.6597*** (0.3778)	
Constant	4.0179*** (0.5306)	2.8561*** (0.5369)	3.9305*** (0.5299)	3.5472*** (0.6038)	4.1410*** (0.5667)	4.1075*** (0.5780)	
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	769	774	774	708	774	774	
R-squared	0.7542	0.7686	0.7611	0.7562	0.7542	0.7527	
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]
Panel B: Alternative sample	Hyperinflation	Financial crisis	Banking crisis	Currency crisis	Inflation crisis	Systemic crisis	New FR
FR dummy	-0.6498** (0.2777)	-1.8407*** (0.3782)	-1.8412*** (0.3505)	-1.9442*** (0.3426)	-1.7268*** (0.3536)	-1.7583*** (0.3404)	-1.7799*** (0.3564)
Constant	1.1860 (0.8114)	3.8387*** (0.5468)	3.9515*** (0.5571)	3.9635*** (0.5367)	4.1182*** (0.5219)	4.1218*** (0.5369)	3.9235*** (0.5338)
Covariates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	494	699	721	710	760	721	774
R-squared	0.7881	0.7661	0.7689	0.7675	0.7575	0.7635	0.7524

Standard errors are in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

7.4 *Placebo test*

Despite several tests being performed, the baseline results have remained unchanged. We now examine whether there are confounding factors that could affect my baseline results, which have remained stable so far. The empirical literature shows that the adoption of an economic policy is generally associated with parallel reforms, making the adoption of fiscal rules a non-random factor (see, for instance, [Sawadogo, 2020](#); [Apeti et al., 2024](#); [Apeti et al., 2025](#)). Therefore, one could imagine that unobservable variables correlated with the adoption of fiscal rules and potentially with the outcome variable could affect the baseline results. Although we know that the empirical method used in this study is intended to address this type of concern, we nevertheless strengthen our results by performing a placebo test on the adoption of fiscal rules. To do this, we set placebo or arbitrary dates for fiscal rules, calculated by randomly assigning episodes of fiscal rules to the countries in our sample after removing the actual years of adoption, i.e. those provided by the database of [Lledó et al. \(2017\)](#). The main idea behind this exercise is that if our results are biased by unobservable variables, the placebo test could also show statistically significant effects. All coefficients obtained are insignificant (see [Table 6](#), columns [1]-[8]). We can therefore conclude that our results are not affected by confounders.

Table 6: Falsification test: placebo

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
VARIABLES								
FR random	0.0170 (0.0866)	0.0804 (0.0691)	-0.0015 (0.0828)	0.0494 (0.0614)	0.0117 (0.0737)	0.0471 (0.0575)	-0.0002 (0.0706)	0.0372 (0.0502)
Constant	1.7858*** (0.0592)	2.1798*** (0.2229)	2.2381*** (0.2378)	2.8215*** (0.3153)	2.2851*** (0.2012)	1.9768*** (0.5093)	2.9022*** (0.2694)	3.2058*** (0.6511)
Covariates	Yes							
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes							
Observations	418	418	418	418	418	418	418	418
R-squared	0.0001	0.4758	0.1591	0.6195	0.2991	0.6658	0.4061	0.7645

Standard errors are in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

8 Heterogeneity

8.1 *Time perspective and dynamics effects*

So far, our results show that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces bank NPLs. Indeed, beyond knowing whether the simple adoption of fiscal rules affects bank NPLs, an even more interesting question is whether this effect persists over time. Fiscal rules have gained in popularity in developing countries, especially since the 2000s, thanks to their ability to reinforce budgetary discipline, improve the credibility of economic policies, and limit the negative effects of electoral cycles or external shocks. At the same time, bank NPLs often operate in a more vulnerable environment: weak institutions, frequent external shocks, uneven banking supervision. Efforts have been made to regulate credit and strengthen balance sheets, which can significantly reduce bank NPLs without being caused by fiscal rule. For example, reforms aimed at improving legal and regulatory frameworks, such as the efficiency of insolvency procedures and the transparency of financial information, also contribute to the reduction of bank NPLs. [World Bank \(2024\)](#) points out that multilateral institutions have injected substantial funding to support the poorest economies, helping stabilize the banking sector. In addition, improved economic growth strengthens borrowers' ability to repay their debts, thus reducing bank NPLs without necessarily being due to the fiscal rule effect. This positive relationship is confirmed by several studies, including those by [Fofack \(2005\)](#); [Gerlach et al. \(2005\)](#); [Mafo Tchinda et al. \(2025\)](#); and [Ghosh \(2015b\)](#), which highlight the importance of macroeconomic stability for the health of the banking sector. In addition, as depositors, banks adjust their asset and liability portfolios in response to economic shocks, including changes in interest

rates and operating costs (Dia, 2013). This can reduce bank NPLs without being due to fiscal rules. To address this issue, we evaluated the effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs over the five years following adoption. This allows us to capture the temporal perspective of fiscal rules on bank NPLs. The results reported in Table 7 panel A columns [1]-[5] show that the effect of the fiscal rule on bank NPLs is persistent over time.

Strange as it may seem, some of those countries who adopted the fiscal rule have subsequently modified, abolished or relaxed these rules in response to economic or political developments. This can lead to a problem known in the literature as “staggered treatment” (see Callaway and Sant’Anna, 2021; Athey and Imbens, 2022; Sun and Abraham, 2021; Goodman-Bacon, 2021). The bias that “staggered treatment” raises is that past treatment can influence the outcome of treatment at a given time, since the treated unit can leave the treatment status and return afterward. For the sake of rigor, we need to use an estimator that can estimate a difference-in-differences specification while taking into account heterogeneous and dynamic treatment effects¹⁰. We follow the difference-in-difference method developed by De Chaisemartin and d’Haultfoeulle (2024). This estimator compares groups whose treatment is changing for the first time with groups whose treatment has not yet changed. In addition, this estimator enables us to test the hypothesis of parallel trends using a placebo analysis, and to calculate the effects of treatment over certain periods after the adoption of fiscal rule.

Figure 4 shows the results of the estimation of the dynamic effects of the adoption of fiscal rules on bank NPLs. Dynamic analysis of the impact of fiscal rules on bank NPLs reveals a three-stage evolution. Before the adoption of fiscal rules, the estimated coefficients are statistically insignificant, validating the hypothesis of a parallel trend between treated and untreated countries. In the first few years following the introduction of the treatment, no immediate effect is observed, suggesting a lag in adjustment between the reform and its impact on the quality of the banking book. It is only from the third post-adoption year onward that the effect becomes progressively significant and negative, reaching as high as -0.5, with a relatively stable trajectory despite moderate confidence intervals. This dynamic reflects the delayed but growing effect of fiscal rules on banking stability, through improvements in fiscal discipline, macroeconomic predictability, and the climate of confidence for financial institutions.

¹⁰We’d like to thank an anonymous referee for suggesting we explore this idea.

Figure 4: *Dynamic effects of FR on bank NPLs applying the dynamic heterogeneity robust difference-in-difference estimator of De Chaisemartin and d’Haultfoeuille (2024). Bars represent 95% confidence intervals around the effects of long-difference tests, the number of placebo (5) and 50 bootstrap replications were applied.*

8.2 The effects by type of fiscal rules

Using the Fiscal Policy and Surveillance Division of the International Monetary Fund Fiscal Affairs Department Fiscal Rules Database, we disaggregate the fiscal rule dummy into four rules: budget balance rules, expenditure rules, revenue rules, and debt rules, as explained in Section 4. The purpose of this exercise is to test the hypothesis that bank NPLs will react differently depending on the type of fiscal rule considered. The results in Table 7 panel B present the conclusions of this hypothesis. With the exception of RR, we find that the adoption of fiscal rules reduces bank NPLs, regardless of the type of fiscal rules implemented. The fact that revenue rules have a non significant effect on the banking sector compared to budget balance rules, expenditure rules, and debt rules can be explained by a number of factors. Indeed, these rules are primarily designed to improve the mobilization of tax resources, without intervening directly in the flow of public spending in the economy. It is mainly budgetary decisions on spending or debt that can directly affect banks through a direct connection. For example, a government deficit rule that requires the state to reduce its borrowing may reduce banks’ opportunities to

invest in government securities, thereby modifying their lending behavior. Conversely, a rule designed to increase tax revenues does not immediately lead to lower spending or a contraction in the credit market. Furthermore, tax increases often target households or businesses without directly impacting the functioning of the banking system. So, although income fiscal rules contribute to overall fiscal balance, their effect on the banking sector remains indirect and generally less marked.

Table 7: Dynamic effect and heterogeneity by type of rule

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Panel A: time perspective					
FR (t+1)	-1.2502*** (0.2985)				
FR (t+2)		-1.2502*** (0.2985)			
FR (t+3)			-1.1845*** (0.2988)		
FR (t+4)				-1.1216*** (0.2993)	
FR (t+5)					-1.0819*** (0.2977)
Constant	4.3658*** (0.4613)	4.3658*** (0.4613)	4.5183*** (0.4771)	4.7009*** (0.4925)	4.8782*** (0.5070)
Main controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	814	814	776	738	699
R-squared	0.7601	0.7601	0.7622	0.7673	0.7729
	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	
Panel B: effects by type of FR					
	ER	BBR	DR	RR	
	-0.1581** (0.0761)	-0.0634*** (0.0607)	-0.4534*** (0.2490)	0.9578 (0.3199)	
Constant	2.8391*** (0.5576)	2.7599*** (0.5898)	3.8123*** (0.6910)	4.8940*** (1.7976)	
Main controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Country/Fe & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	
Observations	814	814	814	814	
R-squared	0.7645	0.7628	0.9319	0.9233	

Standard errors in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.

8.3 *Is credibility of the fiscal rules matter?*

The credibility of a fiscal rule refers to the confidence economic agents have in public authorities' compliance with it. A rule is credible if it is consistently applied and perceived

as binding, even in times of economic or political stress (Kopits and Symansky, 1998). Without credibility, the rule loses its deterrent effect and its ability to stabilize macroeconomic expectations. It anchors market expectations, reduces risk premiums, reinforces budgetary discipline, and limits electoral temptations. Credible rules encourage rigorous management of public finances, improving debt sustainability, and access to long-term financing. A rule that is not credible can be circumvented, suspended, or modified according to the political cycle. This nullifies its disciplinary power, degrades the country’s budgetary reputation, and can worsen borrowing conditions. In this section, we check whether the effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs is strengthened as a function of the level of credibility of fiscal rules. First, we follow Gootjes et al. (2021); Keita and Turcu (2022); Apeti et al. (2024), constructing an index of fiscal rules, considering the four aspects of the rule described in Section 4. We consider five key characteristics of these rules (coverage, legal basis, supporting procedures, enforcement, and flexibility). The resulting index is normalized to unity, so that the fiscal rules index has values between 0 and 5 (see Gootjes et al., 2021; Apeti et al., 2024, for more details). Although higher values of this index indicate strengthening of the rules, we generate a dummy variable (high credibility) that takes the value 1 if the fiscal rule index score of country i at period t is greater than the standard deviation, 0 otherwise (low credibility).

Second, we use institutional quality as a proxy for fiscal rule credibility. In their study, Debrun and Kumar (2009) examine the conditions under which fiscal rules can genuinely improve public finance discipline. Their central argument is that fiscal rules, in and of themselves, are neither inherently good nor bad. Their effectiveness depends largely on the institutional context in which they are implemented. In other words, a fiscal rule is only effective if it is credible, and this credibility is based, above all, on the quality of the institutions that support it. Based on this idea, we calculate a composite index of institutional quality¹¹ and use it as a proxy of the credibility of the fiscal rules. The intuition is that a country with good institutional quality has a high probability of having credible fiscal rules than those with poor institutional quality. The results presented in Table 8 panels A and B show that fiscal rules appear to significantly reduce bank NPLS under both conditions, but with an amplifying effect in countries with high fiscal rule reinforcement (i.e. 2 times higher than in countries with low fiscal rule reinforcement).

¹¹The variables selected are: rule of law, control of corruption, bureaucracy quality, internal conflict, external conflict, investment profile, political risk index, state fragility, and fractionalization index.

Table 8: Credibility of the rules

Panel A: Fiscal rules index		
	[1]	[2]
VARIABLES	Low fiscal rules	Strong fiscal rules
FR dummy	-2.0489*** (0.5207)	-4.0976*** (0.6420)
Constant	5.1566*** (0.8042)	0.3138 (1.0682)
Main controls	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	489	325
R-squared	0.8019	0.8492
Panel B: Proxy for credibility of rules (institutional quality)		
	[1]	[2]
VARIABLES	Low institution	Strong institution
FR adoption	-1.0962*** (0.4000)	-2.0756*** (0.4889)
Constant	5.3375*** (0.7724)	4.1832*** (0.7584)
Main controls	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes
Observations	366	448
R-squared	0.7998	0.8481
Standard errors are in parentheses. *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1.		

8.4 *The contribution of structural factors*

Despite certain common characteristics, developing countries are subject to a number of important structural differences that shape the effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs. Given the heterogeneity in macroeconomic conditions and political situations in developing countries highlighted in the empirical literature (Tapsoba, 2012; Combes et al., 2017; Sawadogo, 2020; Minea et al., 2021; Lin and Ye, 2009; etc.), we explore the sensitivity of our results to these factors. The idea here is that structural factors can magnify or alleviate the effect of fiscal rules on bank NPLs. We follow the literature on impact assessment

(Tapsoba et al., 2012; Sawadogo, 2020; Lin and Ye, 2009; etc.) and assess the effects of this heterogeneity according to the characteristics of the neighborhood: unemployment rate, private credit deposit money, private sector domestic credit, real effective exchange rate, inflation rate, banking crisis, commodity price volatility, oil price, resource rents and rule of law. Given their link to bank NPLs (see, e.g. Zhang et al., 2016; Us, 2017; Ghosh, 2017; Dimitrios et al., 2016; Das and Ghosh, 2007; Bonin et al., 2005; Espinoza and Prasad, 2010; Laeven and Levine, 2009), we hypothesize that the adoption of fiscal rules may have a greater effect in situations characterized by a high level of private credit deposit money, for example. To test this hypothesis, we include an interaction between each of the variables and the fiscal rule. A significant interaction statistic indicates the presence of heterogeneity. The results presented in Table 9, columns [1]-[10], suggest that fiscal rules are more effective when adopted by countries that have a low unemployment rate, high deposit money from private credit, a private sector of high domestic credit, low real effective exchange, a high banking crisis, and a high price of oil.

Table 9: Fiscal rules and nonperforming: structural factors

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]	[10]
FR	-2.5672*** (0.3182)	-1.8313*** (0.2901)	-2.0300*** (0.3202)	-2.0091*** (0.3026)	-1.7938*** (0.3425)	-1.6501*** (0.2947)	-1.5887*** (0.3144)	-0.4179 (0.6408)	-1.5681*** (0.3040)	-1.8773*** (0.6063)
FR*Log Unemployment	0.5157*** (0.0953)									
FR*Private credit deposit money		-0.0119*** (0.0031)								
FR*Domestic credit private sector			-0.0130*** (0.0034)							
FR*Real effective exchange				0.0100*** (0.0034)						
FR*Inflation rate					0.0145 (0.0104)					
FR*Banking crisis						-0.2914** (0.1435)				
FR*Commodity volatility							-0.0128 (0.0399)			
FR*Oil price								-0.0366* (0.0188)		
FR*Resource rents									-0.0053 (0.0109)	
FR*Rule of law										0.5656 (0.9657)
Constant	4.1083*** (0.4771)	4.2343*** (0.5126)	4.8486*** (0.5189)	3.8772*** (0.5101)	4.1174*** (0.5052)	3.9307*** (0.4922)	4.0597*** (0.5047)	4.0575*** (0.4984)	4.0356*** (0.5036)	4.1186*** (0.5214)
Main controls	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes						
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes						
Observations	794	808	704	592	776	814	797	814	814	814
R-squared	0.7460	0.7521	0.7761	0.7531	0.7439	0.7473	0.7434	0.7453	0.7440	0.7438

Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

9 Testing transmission channels

As we identified and explained in Section 3.3, several variables serve as potential channels through which fiscal rules affect bank NPLs. We empirically test some of them—namely GDP per capita (USD), sovereign credit rating, and income inequality. We employ an alternative approach based on unweighted OLS regressions in place of entropy balancing (our baseline specification). While some authors emphasize the importance of maintaining a consistent empirical framework to avoid risks of model selection bias or “cherry-picking” (see, e.g. [Athey and Imbens, 2017](#); [Young, 2019](#); [Gutmann et al., 2023](#)), our deviation is justified on two key grounds. First, the channels analyzed exhibit substantial heterogeneity in terms of statistical structure (e.g., continuous, categorical variables, different frequencies, or data availability), making it impractical to apply entropy balancing consistently across them. Second, these channels are not the main targets of causal identification, but rather serve to illustrate plausible explanatory mechanisms linking fiscal rules to banking outcomes. The use of OLS therefore offers a flexible and transparent framework for testing these mechanisms while maintaining interpretive coherence with the baseline strategy. To test these channels, we proceed in two steps. In the first stage, we tested the relationship between the potential channel and bank NPLs using OLS estimates, controlling for country and year fixed effects. In the second step, we analyze the effects of the fiscal rule adoption treatment on the various potential channels. The idea is that if the potential channel significantly affects bank NPLs and the adoption of fiscal rules has a significant effect on this channel, this channel can be considered a valid channel through which the adoption of fiscal rules reduces bank NPLs. The results of the first step are shown in Table 10 panel A. GDP per capita and sovereign credit rating negatively affect bank NPLs, while income inequality increases them. The results reported in panel B indicate that the adoption of fiscal rules increases GDP per capita and sovereign credit rating, and then reduces income inequality, establishing a close correlation with the channels of transmission. Consequently, GDP per capita, sovereign credit rating, and income inequality are the main potential channels through which fiscal rules reduce bank NPLs.

Table 10: Validity of transmission channels.

	[1]	[2]	[3]
Panel A: effect of potential channels on bank NPLs			
GDP per capita (in USD)	-0.0206*** (0.0075)		
Sovereign credit rating		-0.3486** (0.1358)	
Gini index (income inequality)			0.0534*** (0.0133)
Constant	3.6701*** (0.4715)	5.2980*** (0.5130)	2.7404*** (0.8148)
Observations	814	751	486
R-squared	0.7506	0.7635	0.7876
Main controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes
	[1]	[2]	[3]
Panel B: effect of FR on potential channels			
	GDP per capita (in USD)	Sovereign credit rating	Gini index (income inequality)
FR dummy	0.1343** (1.5775)	0.1206** (0.0667)	-0.4248*** (0.0317)
Constant	2.3563 (2.3348)	1.7330*** (0.1159)	3.4896*** (0.0552)
Observations	1,007	870	551
R-squared	0.3421	0.8304	0.9608
Main controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE & Year/FE	Yes	Yes	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$.

10 Conclusion

Fiscal rules were originally drafted to avoid budget debauchery. Basically, a fiscal rule imposes a lasting constraint on fiscal policy by numerically limiting budget aggregates. In fact, overall they aim to correct the deficit trend and contain excessive spending pressures, particularly in good times, to guarantee fiscal responsibility and public debt sustainability by avoiding the «original sin» phenomenon. These fiscal rules go beyond these main budgetary objectives and act as a stabilizing instrument for monetary policy, since the inflation target could have distracted central banks from their financial stability concerns. This paper establishes the mixed link between fiscal reform and monetary policy. Based on a sample of 62 developing countries over the period 1990-2020, estimates using the entropy balancing method reveal that the adoption of fiscal rules significantly reduces bank NPLs in countries with fiscal rules compared to countries without fiscal rules. In addition, this result proves to be robust in a wide range of alternative specifications, including alternative control variables, different samples, different measures of key variables, and alternative impact assessment methods. Nevertheless, additional estimates reveal that

the effect of adopting fiscal rules on non-performing loan banks is highly heterogeneous, and that, in particular, its importance and magnitude may differ according to certain structural characteristics. In fact, such characteristics may favor or, on the contrary, inhibit the effectiveness of the fiscal rules' monetary framework, and suggest that certain conditions must first be met before we can expect a favorable effect of fiscal rules in terms of reducing bank NPLs.

These results inform policy makers that by adopting fiscal rules, developing countries can not only discipline their fiscal behavior, for example, by limiting political incentives that could undermine its sustainability and effectiveness, but also reduce banks' exposure to sovereign securities. Consequently, provided that it is accompanied by a healthier structural macroeconomic environment, the adoption of fiscal rules can form part of broader policies likely to support monetary policy, post-pandemic recovery, and the mitigation of commodity price effects combined with the Ukraine-Russia crisis in the developing countries.

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Appendix A Data and sample

Table A1 – List of Fiscal Rules (FR) and Non-FR countries

Fiscal rules	Dates	Fiscal rules	Dates	non-Fiscal rules	non-Fiscal rules
Argentina	2000	Nigeria	2007	Albania	Mozambique
Armenia	2002	Pakistan	2005	Bangladesh	Philippines
Brazil	1998	Panama	2002	Belarus	Samoa
Bulgaria	2003	Paraguay	2015	Bolivia	Seychelles
Chile	2001	Peru	2000	Bosnia & Herzegovina	Sierra Leone
Colombia	2000	Poland	1997	Dominican Republic	South Africa
Costa Rica	2001	Portugal	1992	Egypt	Tunisia
Croatia	2009	Romania	2007	El Salvador	Turkey
Ecuador	2003	Rwanda	2013	Ghana	Ukraine
Gabon	2002	Senegal	2000	Guatemala	Uzbekistan
Georgia	2013	Serbia	2011	Honduras	Venezuela
Greece	1992	Slovenia	2000	Jordan	Zambia
India	2004	Tanzania	2013	Lebanon	
Ireland	1992	Thailand	2018	Lesotho	
Kenya	1997	Uganda	2013	Madagascar	
Mauritius	2008	Uruguay	2006	Moldova	
Mexico	2006			Morocco	

Table A2 – List of variables and their sources

Variables	Definition	Sources
1. Dependent variable		
Bank nonperforming loans	Bank nonperforming loans to gross loans (%)	International Monetary Fund, Financial Soundness Indicators.
2. Treatment variable		
Fiscal rules (FR)	Dummy	IMF Fiscal Rules Dataset, Lledo et al. (2017)
budget balance rules (BBR)	Dummy	IMF Fiscal Rules Dataset, Lledo et al. (2017)
Debt rules (DR)	Dummy	IMF Fiscal Rules Dataset, Lledo et al. (2017)
Expenditure rules (ER)	Dummy	IMF Fiscal Rules Dataset, Lledo et al. (2017)
Revenue rules (RR)	Dummy	IMF Fiscal Rules Dataset, Lledo et al. (2017)
3. Baseline model control variables or covariates		
FDI	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)	World Development Indicators (WDI)
Public debt	Public debt (% of GDP)	WDI
Reserve/months	Total reserves in months of imports	WDI
GDP per capita	GDP per capita is gross domestic product (constant 2017 U.S. dollars)	WDI
Capital openness	An index measuring a country's degree of capital account openness	Chinn and Ito (2006)
Inflation targeting	Dummy	Rese (2007) ; Roger (2000) ; Tapsoba et al. (2012) ; Jahan (2012) ; Człkiewicz-Pekala et al. (2019)
Political stability	Index of government quality	Worldwide Governance Indicators database Kaufmann et al. (2011)
Bureaucracy Quality	Index of government quality	Worldwide Governance Indicators database Kaufmann et al. (2011)
4. Additional control variables		
Broad money growth	Broad money growth (% of GDP)	WDI
Fiscal balance	Fiscal balance (% of GDP)	Kese et al. (2017)
Primary balance	Primary balance (% of GDP)	Kese et al. (2017)
Bank concentration (%)	Assets of three largest commercial banks as a share of total commercial banking assets	WDI
Debt service total	Total service debt (% of GDP)	WDI
Bank Z score	It captures the probability of default of a country's commercial banking system.	WDI
Deposit money banks	Total assets held by deposit money banks as a share of GDP	WDI
Unemployment rate	Unemployment rate (Percent of total labor force)	WDI
Financial development	Financial development index	IMF Financial Development database
Government effectiveness	Government effectiveness index	ICRG
Control of corruption	Index ranging from 0 to 100	Worldwide Governance Indicators database Kaufmann et al. (2011)
Rule of law	Rule of Law includes several indicators which measure the extent to which agents have confidence in and abide by the rules of society	Teorell et al. (2020)

Appendix B Robustness and descriptive statistics

Table B1 – Fiscal rules and nonperforming loans—changing covariates

VARIABLES	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]
FR dummy	-1.6534*** (0.4789)	-3.2884*** (0.7996)	-1.0855** (0.4648)	-1.4667* (0.8205)	-1.6771*** (0.4578)	-3.3554*** (0.8128)	-1.1541*** (0.4434)	-1.1067*** (0.8127)
Covariates	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Country/FE	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Year/FE	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Observations	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144	1,144
R-squared	0.0115	0.4279	0.0924	0.4878	0.1069	0.4637	0.1724	0.5150

This table presents the causal impact of fiscal rules on nonperforming loans obtained by weighted least squares regressions changing covariates presented in the tables B3 and B4 . Unreported constant included. Robust standard errors are in parentheses ***p < 0.01, **p < 0.05, *p < 0.1.

Table B2 – Descriptive Statistics of key variables

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
GDP per capita	1822	2.409	5.362	-45.325	81.355
FDI	1799	3.493	4.628	-11.684	81.302
Public debt	1497	54.052	33.649	3.902	319.088
Capital openness	1794	0.062	1.448	-1.927	2.311
Reserves/months	1721	4.606	3.114	0.027	28.549
Inflation targeting	1922	0.323	0.468	0	1
Political stability	1586	0.523	0.137	0.087	0.843
Bureaucracy quality	1469	1.933	0.838	0	4

Table B3 – Covariates balance before weighting

	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]
Descriptive statistics	<i>FR</i>	<i>Non-FR</i>	<i>Difference</i>
Lag FDI	4.19	3.29	-0.90***
Lag inflation rate	4.47	40.48	36.01***
Lag natural resource rents	3.94	4.15	0.21
Lag real GDP per capita growth	2.66	2.36	-0.30**
Lag shocks climate change index	-0.08	0.07	0.15***
Inflation targeting	0.34	0.35	-0.10***

This table shows the sample means before weighting for matching covariates for country-year observations where FR were signed (the treatment group) in column [1] and country-year observations where non-FR were ever signed (the potential control group) in column [2]. Column [3] shows the differences in means and significantly levels between the treatment and control groups. *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Table B4 – Covariates balance after weighting

	[1]	[2]	[3]=[2]-[1]
Covariates balancing	<i>FR</i>	<i>Non-FR</i>	<i>Difference</i>
Lag FDI	4.19	4.19	0.00
Lag inflation rate	4.47	4.47	0.00
Lag natural resource rents	3.94	3.94	0.00
Lag real GDP per capita growth	2.66	2.66	0.00
Lag shocks climate change index	-0.08	-0.08	0.00
Inflation targeting	0.34	0.34	0.00

This table shows the sample means after weighting for matching covariates for country-year observations where FR were signed (the treatment group) in column [1] and country-year observations where non-FR were ever signed (the potential control group) in column [2]. Column [3] shows the differences in means and significantly levels between the treatment and control groups.